

1 **A closer physico-chemical look to the Layer-by-Layer electrostatic**
2 **self-assembly of polyelectrolyte multilayers**

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9 **Published in Advances in Colloid and Interface Science 282 (2020) 102197**

10 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2020.102197>
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31 **Abstract**

32 The fabrication of polyelectrolyte multilayer films (PEMs) using the Layer-by-Layer (LbL)
33 method is one of the most versatile approaches for manufacturing functional surfaces. This is the
34 result of the possibility to control the assembly process of the LbL films almost at will, by
35 changing the nature of the assembled materials (building blocks), the assembly conditions (pH,
36 ionic strength, temperature, etc.) or even by changing some other operational parameters which
37 may impact in the structure and physico-chemical properties of the obtained multi-layered films.
38 Therefore, the understanding of the impact of the above mentioned parameters on the assembly
39 process of LbL materials plays a critical role in the potential use of the LbL method for the
40 fabrication of new functional materials with technological interest. This review tries to provide
41 a broad physico-chemical perspective to the study of the fabrication process of PEMs by the LbL
42 method, which allows one to take advantage of the many possibilities offered for this approach
43 on the fabrication of new functional nanomaterials.

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46 **Keywords:** polyelectrolytes; multilayers; Layer-by-Layer; assembly; nanomaterials

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49 **1. The Layer-by-Layer method: from science to technology**

50 The design of strategies for the modification of surfaces to protect them and avoid aesthetic
51 effects has played an important role on the human technology from the antiquity to current days
52 [1, 2]. This is exemplified in the current interest for the fabrication of coatings with controlled
53 structure and specific functionalities by the modification of surfaces at molecular level, i.e. by a
54 precise control of the structure of the components and their organization at the nanoscale level
55 [3-6]. Functional nano-coatings allow tuning the properties and interactions of surfaces, which
56 in turn are essential aspects on the development of different technological and industrial
57 applications: fabrication of biocompatible films and drug delivery platforms, stabilization of
58 colloidal solutions and particle dispersions, flocculation processes, surface treatments, cosmetics
59 formulations, anticorrosion and antifouling surface and many others [7-11]. The possibility to
60 control the surface properties and chemistry, almost at will, has been possible as result of the
61 combined efforts of researchers belonging to different fields, including physics, chemistry,
62 biology, medicine, engineering or material science [12-16].

63 The fabrication of functional materials with controlled properties in all the three dimensions
64 remains a challenge yet. For much of the 20th century, the manufacturing of soft nano-
65 nanomaterials was dominated by two types of assemblies [4]: the self-assembled monolayers
66 (SAMs), and the Langmuir-Blodgett (LB) and Langmuir-Schaeffer (LS) films. The SAMs are
67 ordered molecular assemblies adsorbed onto surfaces, with their formation being driven by a
68 chemical specific interaction, e.g. thiols onto gold or silanes onto silicon surfaces [17, 18]. On
69 the other side, the building of LB and LS films occurs by transferring amphiphilic molecules
70 from a water/vapor interface onto a solid surface, following a process which enables the
71 deposition of multiple layers. However, these methods are limited to the fabrication of coatings
72 onto flat macroscopic substrates, with a successful film deposition requiring the use of very clean
73 substrates and dust-free atmosphere. Furthermore, LB and LS films present a limited mechanical
74 and thermal resistance, and need long times for its fabrication [19-22]. The limitations of the
75 SAMs, and LB and LS films were partially solved with the introduction of the Layer-by-Layer
76 (LbL) method [11, 23].

77 The LbL method firstly introduced by Iler in the late 60's of the twentieth century for the
78 electrostatic self-assembly of multilayers formed by the alternate deposition of oppositely
79 charged colloidal particles [24] and revisited by Decher et al. [23, 25-28] almost three decades
80 later, is nowadays a mature field which impact in different emerging areas of science and

81 technology. This is mainly the result of the low cost, modularity, versatility and simplicity of
82 this approach on the fabrication of multi-layered materials with tailored structure, well-defined
83 thickness and composition and multiple functionalities, enabling the fabrication of materials
84 including specific chemical, biological, optical, mechanical or electrical properties [9, 11, 29-
85 31]. This has led to a rapid increase of the number of applications of materials obtained by the
86 LbL in different fields of the nanotechnology (interfacial phenomena, colloids, and
87 nanomaterials), including the fabrication of scaffold for tissue engineering, biomedical devices,
88 wound healing dressing, encapsulation platforms, biosensors, cardiovascular devices, implants,
89 conductive layers, perm-selective membranes, sensors, light-emitting thin films, sensors,
90 electrochromic films, photonic systems, non-linear optical devices, antireflection coatings, self-
91 healing and superhydrophobic surfaces [9, 31-44]. Additional indicators of the current interest
92 of the LbL method are the more than 1000 papers related to the topic published each year, and
93 the existence of some commercial products exploiting its advantages, e.g. contact lens coated by
94 LbL films (Ciba Vision, Duluth, GE, USA) or coatings for chromatography column (Agilent
95 Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) [45].

96 The first works dealing with the fabrication of LbL films [25-27] took advantages of the well-
97 known ability of polyelectrolytes to form self-organized supramolecular structures and their
98 capacity to form complexes when are mixed with a polyelectrolytes bearing the opposite charge
99 [46-48]. This allowed the fabrication of ultrathin polyelectrolyte films by the alternate deposition
100 onto flat macroscopic substrates of layers of polyelectrolytes bearing opposite charges (or
101 polyelectrolytes and bolaamphiphilics), the so-called polyelectrolyte multilayers (PEMs).
102 However, the fabrication of LbL multilayers did not remain for long time limited to the
103 electrostatic self-assembly (ESA) of synthetic oppositely charged polyelectrolytes and the list of
104 compounds used for the fabrication of LbL films has been extended to other types of compounds
105 (building blocks), both charged and uncharged, and currently the list includes colloidal particles
106 and nano-objects (graphene and graphene oxide nanoplatelets, carbon nanotubes, dendrimers,
107 clays, microgels, polymeric, ceramic or metallic particles), biomolecules (proteins and peptides,
108 polysaccharides, nucleic acid, lipids), dyes, viruses, synthetic polymers and even in some cases
109 small molecules [33, 38, 49-72].

110 The broad range of compounds that can be assembled using the LbL approach has made it
111 possible the assembly of films using interactions of different nature than the electrostatic one,
112 and there are many examples of the fabrication of LbL films through hydrogen bonding [73, 74],
113 charge transfer interactions [75], molecular recognition [76, 77], coordination interactions [78],

114 chiral recognition [79], host-guest interactions [80], π - π interactions [81], biospecific
115 interactions [82], sol-gel reactions [83], or even covalent bond (“click chemistry” reactions) [84,
116 85]. The only requisite to use an interaction in the fabrication of LbL films is that such interaction
117 must be strong enough to ensure the chemical and mechanical integrity of material when they
118 are exposed to stresses.

119 It has been stated that the LbL method was designed for the deposition of multi-layered coatings
120 onto flat which means that the LbL approach must be considered as a template-assisted assembly
121 methodology. Therefore, the fabrication of LbL films requires a precursor substrate, sacrificial
122 or not, that supports the assembly of the layers. Nowadays, the fabrication of LbL materials is
123 possible using any type of solvent accessible surface as template, independently of its chemical
124 nature, shape, geometry or size. Thus, the fabrication of LbL coating onto substrates which differ
125 from the traditionally used macroscopic solid charged substrates is common, with colloidal
126 micro- and nanoparticles, liposomes or vesicles, micelles, fluid interfaces (floating multilayers),
127 emulsion droplets or even cells being some of the currently used templates [86-94]. The substrate
128 may play different roles in the LbL assembly: (i) provides the geometry and morphology to the
129 assembled material, remaining as a part of the final material once the deposition of the film is
130 finished, or (ii) is only used as a template during the assembly process, and afterwards it can
131 be removed from the final material through chemical or physical procedures, allowing the
132 fabrication of free-standing LbL materials, e.g. hollow capsules [95, 96]. The versatility of the
133 LbL method provides the bases for a careful control on the size, shape and morphology of the
134 assembled materials, which allows the fabrication of different types of materials, from flat films
135 to nano- and micro-capsules [29, 92, 97], and even multicapsules including several hierarchically
136 organized nano-containers [98-102]. Furthermore, sophisticated materials including particles
137 with onion-like structures, sponges, membranes or nanotubes have also been manufactured taking
138 advantage of the versatility and modularity of the LbL method [40, 103, 104]. Figure 1 presents
139 some of the advantages and characteristics that made of the LbL method a key enabling
140 technology on the fabrication of supramolecular materials with defined architecture.

141 Most of the studies on LbL materials, both theoretical and experimental, have paid attention to
142 the growth mechanisms of the films, i.e. the dependence of the adsorbed amount of material on
143 the number of adsorbed bilayers, N , and their potential applications [11]. However, there is an
144 important lack of knowledge about certain aspects related to the physico-chemical bases
145 underlying the formation of the LbL films and their properties. This is especially important when
146 the internal structure and molecular properties of LbL multilayers, and their correlations are

147 concerned [105-112]. The understanding of such aspects may only be obtained through a careful
148 examination of the different variables that allows tuning the fabrication of LbL materials [113]:
149 charge density of the assembled compounds and of the substrates [49, 114, 115], concentration
150 [116], polyelectrolyte molecular weights [117], ionic strength [107, 111], solvent quality for the
151 building blocks [118], pH [51, 119] and temperature [120]. The understanding of the impact of
152 such parameters on the structure of the multilayers plays an essential role on the fabrication of
153 supramolecular materials with controlled and tunable structures and physico-chemical
154 properties. Therefore, the fabrication of materials with technological application making use of
155 the LbL approach is a multidisciplinary challenge needing the study of the physico-chemical
156 bases underlying the fabrication process. This review discusses the current understanding of the
157 most relevant physico-chemical aspects for the application of LbL polyelectrolyte films in
158 different technological and industrial fields. The extension of the research on LbL films makes
159 it difficult to present a detailed discussion of the topic. Therefore, this work is focused on the
160 study of those systems where electrostatic interactions play an important role on the assembly
161 process, i.e. the assembly of polyelectrolyte multilayers. It is expected that the discussion
162 contained in this review can help to close the gap between the physico-chemical knowledge on
163 LbL polyelectrolyte multilayers and functional parameters with impact on the development of
164 advances applications of this type of materials.

165
166 Figure 1. Advantages and characteristics of the LbL approach for the fabrication of functional
167 materials.

168

169 2. Fabrication methods of Layer-by-Layer films

170 The fabrication of LbL films requires to establish assembly protocols taking into consideration
171 that polyelectrolyte multilayers are thermodynamically unstable systems with respect to the
172 formation of the respective inter-polyelectrolyte complexes in solution [113]. This is because the
173 erosion of polymer chains from the multilayers is associated with a gain of the translational and

174 configurational entropy of the chains, i.e. the mobility of the chains in the solution is higher than
175 that of adsorbed molecules in the multilayer [16]. Furthermore the design of LbL materials with
176 true technological applications requires the assembly methodologies easily scalable from the
177 laboratory to an industrial level, which makes it necessary to engineer the LbL materials
178 following the same rules used for the fabrication of bulk materials [121].

179 The LbL method is a simple and inexpensive procedure for the fabrication of multi-layered
180 structures [58, 122]. Most of the LbL materials continue being assembled following procedures
181 that are reminiscent from that introduced by the seminal works by Decher et al. [28]. This
182 involves the deposition of the multilayers upon dipping the substrates into solutions of the
183 components to be assembled. However, the adaption of the assembly process to the specific
184 nature of the used templates (morphology, size or chemical nature) has required of slight
185 modifications on the fabrication to manufacture an extraordinary variety of novel thin film
186 materials. It is worth mentioning that the methodology used for the assembly influences strongly
187 the properties of the obtained films, and their choice is depending on the final application of the
188 material [123, 124].

189 Figure 2 shows a scheme representing the dipping deposition method for the deposition of LbL
190 films onto flat macroscopic substrates. The deposition by dipping relies on the alternate
191 immersion of the substrate into solutions containing the interacting compounds (polyelectrolyte
192 bearing charges with the opposite sign or other type molecules), with intermediate rinsing steps
193 between two consecutive adsorption steps [125]. This rinsing steps ensure that the material
194 weakly adsorbed to the layer may be removed which avoid the cross-contamination during the
195 assembly process. This is especially important when the assembly of polyelectrolyte is
196 concerned because the formation of inter-polyelectrolyte complexes can result on their
197 undesirable precipitation onto the LbL films, which may impact on the composition, structure
198 and properties of the assembled material [45, 125]. It is worth mentioning that some attempts
199 have been done to avoid the intermediate rinsing steps during the assembly of the LbL films,
200 with dewetting method being a promising alternative for such purpose [126, 127]. The dewetting
201 method involves the doping of the solution of the adsorbing compound with an organic solvent
202 (dimethylformamide or dimethylsulfoxide), with the evaporation of such organic solvent and the
203 subsequent dewetting process of the polymeric layer playing an essential role of the control of
204 the layer deposition [126]. This makes that the time required for the assembly of the material can
205 be reduced almost 30 times [127]. Another alternative on the seeking of faster deposition
206 methodologies is to include a constant stirring, using a magnetic bar, of the solutions during the

207 immersion of the substrates into the solution which allows limiting the deposition times to 10-
208 20 seconds [128].

209 The fabrication of LbL films using the alternated dipping is rather slow because each adsorption
210 and rinsing step requires several minutes (around 15 minutes per each deposition step) to ensure
211 the diffusion of the molecules to the surface, their adsorption and the equilibration of the
212 deposited films, which is a limitation for the industrial application of dipping deposition [44, 45,
213 129-131]. This has led to the implementation of different automatic dipping devices, which
214 makes it easy the deposition process, even though the time required for the assembly of the
215 materials remains long. However, the use of automatic dippers allowing the rotation of the
216 substrate during its immersion in the solution provides the bases for an increase of 3-10 times of
217 the deposition velocity, with the rotation velocity enabling the control of the layer thicknesses
218 (thicker films are obtained by the increase of the rotation velocity).

219
220 Figure 2. Scheme representing the different steps of the fabrication of LbL films by dipping.

221
222 The operational simplicity of the LbL approach has contributed to its adaptation to a broad range
223 of situations. The spin coating and spray-assisted deposition are two methodological approaches,
224 allowing for a speeding up the deposition process of LbL films [129, 132-135]. These approaches
225 allows overcoming some of the main limitations of the assembly by dipping (time required for
226 the fabrication of LbL films and difficulties for scaling-up), without compromising the properties
227 of the obtained film properties. This is key on the development of LbL nanomaterials at the
228 industrial scale. Figure 3 shows schemes of the spin coating and the spray-assisted deposition
229 approaches.

230

231 Figure 3. Scheme of the deposition of LbL films using spin-coating (a) and spray-assisted
 232 deposition (b).

233

234 The use of spin coating on the fabrication of thin films relies on the casting of the solution
 235 containing the compound to be assembled onto the substrate surface. Afterwards, the substrate
 236 undergo spinning at a constant velocity until the spreading of homogenous film onto the substrate
 237 and the complete evaporation of the solvent are attained. Once the layer is deposited, this is
 238 rinsed following a procedure analogous to that applied during the layer fabrication, with the
 239 substrate remaining under spinning until the total drying of the film is ensured. The repetition of
 240 the deposition and rinsing spinning cycles allows manufacturing multi-layered films [136, 137].
 241 The use of spin coating deposition provides the bases for obtaining films with lower roughness
 242 and better organization than those obtained using the dipping approach, and a low degree of
 243 interpenetration between adjacent layers. This is explained considering the complex interplay
 244 between electrostatic and hydrodynamic interactions (centrifugal, air shear, and viscous forces)
 245 involved in the spinning-assisted deposition, with the former leading to the adsorption and
 246 rearrangement of polymers, and the latter governing the desorption of the weakly bound material
 247 from the surface and the dehydration of the films [137]. The intricate balance between
 248 electrostatic and hydrodynamic interactions helps to explain that spin coating can be several
 249 order of magnitude faster than dipping and the smaller thickness of the obtained films, with the
 250 latter being related to the spinning velocity (higher velocities lead to thinner films). Furthermore,

251 spin-coating deposition leads to a significant reduction the amount of material required for the
252 deposition of the layers [137]. However, the advantages of spin-coating cannot overcome the
253 important drawbacks associated with the low volatility of the water which is the solvent
254 commonly used for LbL assembly, limiting the practical application of spin-coating on LbL
255 deposition. It is worth noting that the success of the deposition of layers using spin-coating
256 requires a careful control of the spinning velocity and solution concentration, with both
257 parameters being essential affecting to the thickness of the deposited layers [138].

258 An alternative way for exploiting the rotation of the substrate on the fabrication of LbL films is
259 the deposition under high-gravity fields, using rotating media, introduced by Ma et al. [139] for
260 the fabrication of multilayers formed by poly(ethylenimine) (PEI) and zirconia nanoparticles.
261 The main advantage of this deposition methodology is associated with the hastening of the
262 diffusion process, which shortens the time required for reaching the adsorption equilibrium. This
263 methodology provides the bases for obtaining LbL films with similar quality than those obtained
264 by dipping, with a less time consumption, which is rationalized considering the increase in the
265 concentration gradient and the importance of the turbulence in the deposition process.

266 The use of the spray-assisted deposition for the fabrication of LbL materials was firstly
267 introduced by Schlenoff et al. [140] for the alternate deposition of poly(4-styrene sulfonate of
268 sodium) (PSS) and poly(diallyl-dimethylammonium chloride) (PDADMAC), and relies on the
269 deposition of layers by an alternate spraying of solutions containing different materials onto the
270 surface of a flat substrate, with intermediate rising cycling between the deposition of two
271 adjacent layers. It is worth noting that most of the advantages stated for the spin-coating
272 assembly also apply when the spray-assisted deposition is concerned [140], with the roughness
273 and the thickness of the multilayers obtained by spraying being significantly smaller than those
274 of films obtained by dipping [124, 141-143]. This may be understood considering the
275 coexistence of two simultaneous process during the spraying of the solutions: (i) adsorption and
276 (ii) drainage. This requires performing the spraying perpendicularly to the surface to ensure the
277 gravitational drainage which favours a fast removal of the excess of sprayed solution. However,
278 the gravitational drainage may lead the inhomogeneous films, with an enhanced deposition close
279 to the solution drips [134, 144]. This may be partially solved by using rotating substrate during
280 the deposition process [145-147]. The spray-assisted deposition allows the reduction of the
281 contact time (less than 10 second may be enough) between the adsorbing material and the surface
282 which results on a limited interpenetration between adjacent layers [134]. This has led to a strong
283 development of the application of spray-assisted deposition at industrial level [44, 148]. A

284 further advantage of the spray-assisted deposition of LbL films is that this methodological
 285 approach enables a fast fabrication of uniform LbL films on substrates with a large area [4, 149].
 286 The deposition by spraying can be furtherly sped-up using vacuum which allows minimizing the
 287 lag time between the different steps involved in the fabrication process [44]. The effectiveness
 288 of the spray-assisted deposition requires the optimization of the spray-substrate distance and the
 289 times of spraying and draining [44]. Furthermore, the solution concentrations, the volume and
 290 flow of the sprayed solutions, the spraying time and the waiting time between two consecutive
 291 steps and whether rinsing steps are included or not are essential and how long these rinsing steps
 292 are important aspects to considered when the fabrication of materials using the spray-assisted
 293 deposition is concerned [134, 140, 143-145, 150-152]. Table 1 summarized some differences on
 294 the characteristic of the films obtained using the traditionally dipping deposition and spin-coating
 295 or spray-assisted deposition.

296 Table 1. Characteristic of LbL films obtained using dipping deposition and spin-coating or spray-
 297 assisted deposition.

Dipping	Spin-coating/Spray-assisted deposition
Thick	Thin
Rough	Smooth
Interpenetrated	Stratified
Opaque	Transparent

298

299 An alternative to the conventional spray-assisted LbL deposition consists in the simultaneous
 300 spraying of two or more interacting species against a substrate, the so-called simultaneous spray
 301 coating of interacting species (SSCIS). This type of spray-assisted deposition leads to a fast
 302 interaction between the complementary species on the surface, enabling a continuous and
 303 gradual growth of the films. The thickness of the obtained layers depends on the spraying time,
 304 with the solvent and excess of material being removed by drainage [151, 153]. It is worth
 305 mentioning that the thicknesses of the multilayers fabricated by the SSCIS approach were found
 306 to be similar to those of films obtained using the conventional alternate spray-assisted approach
 307 [153].

308 The use of electric or magnetic fields can help on the deposition of LbL films [154, 155]. This
 309 leads to denser and thicker films than any other technique used on the assembly of LbL materials
 310 [156, 157]. The application of electric field is generally based in the use of electrodes as
 311 templates for the assembly of the films (electrodeposition). This allows the deposition of the

312 films by the application of a voltage in electrolytic cells. The standard electrodeposition approach
313 for the fabrication of LbL films requires the immersion of two electrodes in the solution of the
314 polymer to be deposit, followed by the application of an electric current within the deposition
315 cell to drive the formation of the layer. Once the layer is deposited, the electrodes are rinsed with
316 the solvent, and then they are placed in a solution containing the compound forming the second
317 layer and the process is repeated [158]. Several experimental designs has been used for
318 optimizing the electrodeposition of LbL films, which can be applied to the deposition of multi-
319 layered structures onto macroscopic surfaces or colloidal particles [127]. The control of the
320 thickness and roughness of the electrodeposited films can be done optimizing the applied voltage
321 and the time of the process [159].

322 The fabrication of electrodeposited films can be performed taking advantage of local effects
323 appearing at the electrodes surfaces, e.g. redox reactions or pH changes. Therefore, the presence
324 of electrodes may induce a local pH change in their vicinity in relation to that of the solution,
325 with the existence of a lower value of pH close to the anode which allows the deposition [160].
326 However, this approach is limited to the deposition of a few layer because the formation of a
327 layer reduce the penetration of the current towards the electrode, with the disappearance of and
328 the effect of the pH change.

329 Magnetic fields can be also exploited for the deposition of LbL films [161]. This approach is
330 based in the immersion of the substrates in solutions containing charged magnetic sensitive
331 materials, which are deposited following the traditional LbL dipping approach. Magnetic fields
332 are applied between the deposition steps of two adjacent layers to control the packing of the
333 layers, and consequently the multilayer thickness [162].

334 The above discussion was devoted so far of the fabrication of LbL films onto macroscopic
335 surfaces. However, many applications of LbL materials are associated with the encapsulation of
336 active compounds [9, 38, 104]. This makes it necessary to design deposition methodologies
337 enabling the use of colloidal particles, micelles, liposomes, vesicles or emulsion drops as
338 templates. The use of colloidal templates in LbL deposition is based in the deposition by
339 immersion (dipping) firstly introduced by Decher et al. [28]. However, some modifications must
340 be introduced on the deposition procedure accounting for the specific characteristics of the
341 colloidal substrates [86, 87, 163].

342 One of the most important aspects to consider, when colloidal substrates are used as template for
343 LbL deposition, is that these are commonly dissolved or suspended in a solvent, generally water.

344 The seminal works dealing with the LbL coating of colloidal particles were done by the group
345 of Möhwald in the late 90's of the past century [86, 87, 164]. Their approach was based on the
346 alternate deposition of polyelectrolytes bearing opposite charges onto colloidal microparticles
347 which intermediate washing cycles. This allows the fabrication of both core-shell structures and
348 hollow capsule. The template on the latter cases is a sacrificial substrate which can be removed
349 in a final step, generally by a chemical dissolution process. This depends on the chemical nature
350 of the colloidal template, e.g. fluoride acid is used for removing SiO₂ particles, diluted
351 hydrochloride acid for melamine formaldehyde resins and tetrahydrofuran when polystyrene
352 latex particles are used as templates [11]. One of the most important challenges in the preparation
353 of LbL materials using colloidal templates is the separation of the excess of non-adsorbed
354 material from the dispersion containing the particles capped with the multilayer. This is
355 affordable when microparticles are used as templates by the centrifugation of the suspension
356 after the adsorption step. The centrifugations leads to the sedimentation of the decorated particles
357 sediment at the bottom which allows removing the supernatant, where the excess of non-
358 adsorbed material remains. Once the supernatant is removed, the particles are re-dispersed in an
359 aqueous medium, and the centrifugation-re-dispersion steps are repeated, commonly three times,
360 to ensure that the material excess is completely removed. Once the clean suspension of particles
361 decorated with the multi-layered structure is obtained, the adsorption of the next layer is
362 performed repeating the sequence of adsorption and cleaning. This methodology minimizes the
363 production of insoluble inter-polyelectrolyte complexes in the aqueous phase during the
364 assembly process [165, 166]. Figure 4 shows a sketch of the different steps involved on the
365 deposition of polyelectrolyte multilayers onto a negatively charged particle.

366 The application of the above described methodology is difficult when nano-sized colloids are
367 chosen as templates. This is because their sedimentation using centrifugation is not easy and the
368 application of alternative procedures for the separation of the particles decorated with the
369 multilayers and the excess of non-adsorbed material are required [167]. One of the most
370 promising alternatives for such purpose is the serum replacement method, which also helps on
371 the preparation of highly concentrated capsule suspensions [168]. It is worth mentioning that the
372 use of filtration processes, e.g. serum replacement, for the separation of the capsules and the
373 excess of non-adsorbed material provides the bases for increase the velocity of the LbL
374 assembly, enhancing the recovery yield. The latter is essential for an industrial scaling up of the
375 assembly process, with the preparation of concentrated capsules suspensions remaining as an
376 important challenge for the LbL method. This has been partially resolved by using tubular flow

377 type reactors, which allows preparing capsules with the required number of layers following a
378 procedure of production in continuous. However, a limitation for such method is that a reduced
379 amount of the polyelectrolyte forming the last deposited layers always remains in solution after
380 each deposition step, which can lead to cross-contamination as result of the formation of inter-
381 polyelectrolyte complexes [169].

382
383 Figure 4. Scheme representing the methodology used for the fabrication of LbL materials using
384 as template a negatively charged colloidal microparticle. The representation shows the layers
385 assembly steps, and the final treatment for removing the template to obtain a hollow capsule.

386
387 The above described approaches are generally useful when particles with higher density than the
388 water are used. However, the use of particles lighter than water (e.g. emulsion drops, vesicles or
389 liposomes) needs to adapt the methodology, and in particular the separation methodologies. In
390 the particular case of the deposition of LbL films onto vesicles or liposomes, the procedure can
391 be summarized in the following steps [170]: (i) a solution containing the material to be assembled
392 in the first layer is added to a diluted suspension containing the vesicles or liposomes; (ii) once
393 the first layer is deposited, a solution containing the material used for the second layer is added
394 to the dispersion of coated vesicles or liposomes and the deposition of the layer occurs, whereas
395 the excess of polyelectrolyte leads to the formation of inter-polyelectrolyte complexes with the
396 non-adsorbed polyelectrolyte remaining in the solution after the first adsorption step. This inter-
397 polyelectrolyte complexes are depleted as a precipitate form the solution; (iii) centrifugation of
398 the dispersion to enhance the separation of the precipitated inter-polyelectrolyte complexes and
399 the supernatant containing the capsules. The application of the centrifugation is possible because

400 the formation of the polyelectrolyte shell provides enough rigidity to the vesicles/liposomes,
401 avoiding their aggregation and fusion; and (iv) after the deposition of the first bilayer, the process
402 can be repeated several times up to the required number of layers is obtained. However, the
403 formation of inter-polyelectrolyte, which may form supramolecular aggregates with the
404 decorated liposomes, and the centrifugation process leads to a reduction of around 5% of the
405 total number of liposomes/vesicles after each adsorption/separation cycle, which limits the
406 number of layers to values no higher than 10-12 [170]. It is worth mentioning that the use of
407 emulsion drops, in particular of oil in water emulsions, as templates for the deposition of LbL
408 films has received a big attention in recent years. This is because emulsion drops can be used as
409 reservoir where an active molecules can be solubilized, enhancing its bioavailability [171-174].

410 One of the most important challenge of the fabrication of LbL films onto light-weight colloidal
411 templates is to avoid the centrifugation steps because it can lead to the aggregation of the
412 templates and/or the formed capsules. A possible alternative for accomplishing such purpose is
413 to remove the cleaning step from the fabrication procedure by the addition of the exact amount
414 of polyelectrolyte required for reaching the surface saturation [86, 175]. The saturation method
415 allows the fabrication of supramolecular structures to those obtained by the introduction of
416 centrifugation steps, with an increase of the velocity of the assembly process by a factor 3 [86,
417 174]. The optimization of the saturation procedure requires a careful examination of the zeta
418 potential values during the deposition procedure [86].

419 Another alternative for avoiding the centrifugation is to immobilize the particles in an agarose
420 hydrogel. This allows one to consider the particles collected within the immobilization matrix as
421 a planar substrate where the deposition can be performed using the traditional dipping approach.
422 Once the desired number of layer are deposited, the agarose hydrogel can be removed by a
423 heating procedure (at 37°C) followed by a cleaning procedure based on the repetition of
424 centrifugation-re-dispersion cycles at least three times. The use of this type of deposition results
425 on the formation of thinner films than those obtained using the conventional approach used for
426 coating colloidal particles, which may be explained in terms of a limited diffusion of the polymer
427 through the agarose hydrogel [176].

428 In recent years, the use of microfluidic systems for the fabrication of LbL films is gaining
429 interest. This type of devices enables the deposition of LbL layers onto both the channel walls
430 and substrates placed or immobilized within the channels [177-180]. The most common
431 approach for taking advantage of the microfluidic on the fabrication of LbL films involves the

432 use of pressure or vacuum to drive the sequential displacement of the polymer and washing
433 solutions within the microfluidic chips, with the time of contact being the most important factor
434 governing the deposited amounts [181-183]. The interesting perspectives that microfluidic opens
435 in LbL deposition are limited by the difficulties associated with the optimization of the assembly
436 process in each particular case and the high price of the instrumentation [127].

437 The above discussion shows clearly that LbL deposition can be performed independently on the
438 chemical composition or surface charge of the substrate. Furthermore, it is worth mentioning
439 that, in most of the cases, the thickness of the layers appears to be rather independent on the
440 substrate, thus after the deposition of a certain number of layers, i.e. once a certain degree of
441 coverage has been reached, the deposition of additional layers is not significantly affected by the
442 surface nature [45]. Furthermore, a detailed understanding of the LbL assembly of
443 polyelectrolyte multilayers makes it necessary to explore the physico-chemical aspects
444 influencing the formation process and the final properties of the films, with two aspects being
445 essential for such understanding: (i) polyelectrolyte multilayers are highly hydrated systems and
446 contain counterions, and (ii) the adsorption of polyelectrolyte layers is almost irreversible.

447

448 **3. Physico-chemical aspects of the electrostatically-driven Layer-by-Layer method**

449 **3.1. Growth mechanisms of Layer-by-Layer multilayers**

450 One of the most important aspect of the LbL method is the possibility of tuning the thickness of
451 the films almost at will. This requires a careful examination of the dependences of the adsorbed
452 amount (or layer thickness) on the number of bilayers, N , i.e. the growth mechanism. Two
453 different dependences are frequently found for the growth of PEMS: linear and non-linear, with
454 the latter being generally referred in the literature as exponential growth, even though the
455 dependence of the adsorbed amount on the number of bilayer is not truly exponential (Notice
456 that the films are denoted as $(A - B)_n$, with A and B representing the interacting species
457 (commonly polycation and polyanion, respectively) and the subindex n representing the number
458 of bilayers). Figure 5 presents a scheme of the two common growth dependences appearing in
459 LbL films.

460 The existence of linear growth is characterized by a quasi-linear dependence of the adsorbed
461 amount on the number of bilayers, i.e. the adsorbed amount increases quasi-linearly upon the
462 adsorption of a bilayers. In most of the case, polyelectrolyte multilayers presenting a linear

463 growth evidence an increase of the thickness around a few nanometers after the adsorption of a
464 bilayer, which is roughly the sum of the characteristic lengths of the polycation and the
465 polyanion. This thickness can be modified by playing with the conformation of the
466 polyelectrolytes in the solution, which is possible by the modification of the assembly conditions,
467 i.e. the charge density for weak polyelectrolytes or the balance of interactions occurring in the
468 solution. The linear growth is generally found in (PAH - PSS)_n multilayers (with PAH being
469 poly(allylamine hydrochloride)) almost independently on the assembly conditions and for
470 (PDADMAC -PSS)_n films assembled under conditions in which a high effective charge density
471 exists in both polyelectrolytes (commonly assembled from low ionic strength solutions) [184,
472 185]. Other examples of multilayers growing in a linear way are (PAH - PAA)_n (PAA being and
473 (PM2VP - PSS)_n (with PAA and PM2VP being poly(acrylic acid) and poly(N-methyl-2-vinyl
474 pyridinium chloride), respectively) [186] The non-linear growth is characterized by an increase
475 of the adsorbed amount faster than that found in a linear growth (supra-linear dependence).
476 Among the systems presenting non-linear growth are accounted multilayers combining
477 PDADMAC and PSS assembled under conditions in which a reduced effective charge exists in
478 the polyelectrolytes (generally LbL films assembled from solutions with high ionic strength)
479 [107, 111, 118, 187], and different multilayers including biopolymers among their components,
480 e.g. (CHI - PAA)_n, (PLL - HA)_n or (PLL - PGA)_n –with CHI, PLL, HA and PGA being chitosan,
481 poly(L-lysine), hyaluronic acid and poly(glutamic acid), respectively- [50, 51, 188-190]. Table
482 1 reports some examples of multilayers growing linearly and non-linearly.

483
484 Figure 5. Scheme representing an idealization of the two common growth dependences
485 appearing in LbL films: linear and non-linear.

486

487 Table 2. Summary of some multilayers presenting linear growth and non-linear growth.

System	Ref.	Notes
<i>Linear Growth PEMs</i>		
(PDMAEMA-PSS) _n	[49]	
(PDADMAC-PSS) _n	[89, 107, 111, 118, 184, 191]	PDADMAC with a high effective charge density (low ionic strength conditions)
(PAA – PLL) _n	[117]	Assembly using polyelectrolytes with low molecular weight
(PAH - PAA) _n	[119, 186]	Assembly dependent on the pH and charge density of the polymers
(PAH-PSS) _n	[184, 185, 191]	Almost independent on the conditions used for the assembly
(PM2VP - PSS) _n	[186]	
(PDMA - PMAA) _n	[192]	
(PEI - DNA) _n	[193]	
(PEI - BSA) _n	[194]	
(PEI - PAA) _n	[195]	
(CHI – CMC) _n	[196]	
(CHI - ALG) _n	[197, 198]	
(PEI - ALG) _n	[197]	
<i>Non-Linear Growth PEMs</i>		
(CHI - PAA) _n	[50, 51, 199]	
(PDADMAC-PSS) _n	[89, 107, 111, 118, 184, 191]	PDADMAC with a low effective charge density (low ionic strength conditions)
(PAH - PAA) _n	[119]	Assembly dependent on the pH and charge density of the polymers
(PAH-PSS) _n	[120]	Assembly at high temperatures (T > 55 ° C)
(PLL - HA) _n	[188, 189, 200, 201]	
(PAH - HA) _n	[199]	
(CHI - HA) _n	[199, 202]	
(PLL - PGA) _n	[203]	
(CHI - PGA) _n	[204]	
(CHI - FUC) _n	[205]	
(PLL - HEP) _n	[206]	
(CHI - HEP) _n	[207]	

488 ¹ PDMAEMA: triblock copolymer PDMAEMA-PCL-PDMAEMA, with PDMAEMA and PCL being poly[2-
489 (N,N-dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate) and poly(epsilon-caprolactone), respectively; PSS: poly(4-
490 styrenesulfonate of sodium); PDADMAC: poly(diallyl-dimethylammonium chloride); PAA: poly(acrylic acid);
491 PLL: poly(L-lysine); PAH: poly(allylamine hydrochloride); PM2VP: poly(N-methyl-2-vinyl pyridinium
492 chloride); CHI: chitosan; HA: hyaluronic acid; PDMA: poly(2-(Dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate); PMAA:
493 poly(methacrylic acid); PEI: poly(ethylenimine); DNA: Desoxyribonucleic acid; BSA: bovine serum albumine;
494 CMC: carboxy(methyl cellulose); ALG: alginate; PGA: poly(glutamic acid); FUC: fucoidan; HEP: heparin

495

496 The differences in the dependence of the adsorbed amount on the number of bilayers appearing
497 in polyelectrolyte multilayers have been justified in terms of different physical mechanisms. The
498 first attempt for providing a physical picture accounting for such differences was performed by
499 Elbert et al. [7]. They consider the existence of diffusion of the polyelectrolytes within the
500 multilayer structure in both linear and non-linear growth multilayers. However, such mobility of
501 the chains presents subtle differences depending on the nature of the polyelectrolytes, and the

502 type of growth. The study by Elbert et al. [7] assumed that the formation of linear growth
503 multilayers occurs by an initial deposition of molecular polyelectrolyte layers, which can be
504 strongly intermingled due to the diffusion of the polyelectrolyte chains within the perpendicular
505 direction to the film surface, resulting in a blend layer. The final thickness of such films is
506 determined by the molecular weights and the charge characteristics of the polyelectrolytes. The
507 situation was found to be slightly more complex when multilayers presenting a non-linear growth
508 were analysed. This type of growth is assumed to be driven for the deposition of more than one
509 layer in each deposition cycle, which should be limited as result of the strong repulsion between
510 polyelectrolytes chains. However, this may occur considering that the diffusion of
511 polyelectrolytes within the multilayers structure may results in some cases (specific
512 polyelectrolyte mixtures and assembly conditions) in a coacervation process between the
513 polyelectrolyte in solution and the oppositely charged polyelectrolyte chains diffusing from the
514 multilayer. These coacervates can precipitate onto the multilayer surface resulting in an increase
515 of the thickness higher to than expected for a molecular layer [208, 209] in agreement with the
516 theoretical studies by Tang and Besseling [210]. These latter author found a correlation between
517 the behaviour of inter-polyelectrolyte complexes in solution and that corresponding to
518 polyelectrolyte multilayers. Furthermore, the existence of different dynamics of the
519 polyelectrolytes in linear and non-linear growth multilayers are in agreement with the finding by
520 Xu et al. [211]. They attributed the transition from linear growth films to non-linear growth one
521 in (PDMA-PMAA)_n multilayers to a change on the dynamics of the polyelectrolytes changed
522 occurring as result of a modification of the ionic pairing within the multilayer.

523 An alternative explanation that rule out the role of the diffusion in linear growth polyelectrolyte
524 multilayers was proposed by Picart et al. [188, 189, 200, 201, 212]. They explained that non-
525 linear growth for (PLL – HA)_n multilayers results from an *in* and *out* diffusion of one of the
526 polyelectrolytes within the multilayer structure. In particular, this diffusion of the PLL chains
527 diffusion within the multilayer structure was found, with this diffusion being depending on the
528 nature of the solution interacting with the multilayer. Thus, the exposure of (PLL – HA)_n to PLL
529 solutions leads to a diffusion of the polyelectrolyte to the inner of the multilayer, whereas the
530 opposite in true when the multilayers are exposed to HA solutions. The diffusion of the PLL to
531 the solution-film interface drives the PLL-HA complexation, favouring the adsorption of more
532 HA than that corresponding to a single monolayer, with the overall growth resembling a situation
533 in which each bilayer is thicker than those expected from the molecular sizes of the
534 polyelectrolytes, resulting in a non-linear growth of the film [188]. The diffusion of

535 polyelectrolytes on (PLL - HA)_n films was furtherly analysed by Picart et al. [212] using confocal
536 laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) to monitor the adsorption process within the axis
537 perpendicular to the multilayer by adding fluorescently labelled polyelectrolytes at different
538 height of the multilayer. The results showed that whereas the fluorescently labelled PLL was
539 able to diffuse within the entire multilayer, the fluorescently labelled HA remained at the fixed
540 positions where it were assembled. This was claimed by Picart et al. [212] and by Lavalle et al.
541 [213] as a clear evidence of the role of the interdiffusion of at least one of the polyelectrolyte,
542 and in some cases both of them -(PLL-PGA)_n films-, as driving force of the non-linear growth
543 [182]. However, the works by Picart et al. [188, 212] were only focused on films with non-linear
544 growth, and no control experiments on multilayers presenting linear growth were included. Thus,
545 even the driving force of the non-linear growth proposed by Picart et al. [188] agrees
546 qualitatively with the picture provided by Elbert et al. [7], i.e. diffusion of one of the
547 polyelectrolytes combined with the coacervation and precipitation of inter-polyelectrolyte
548 complexes onto the polyelectrolyte surface, Picart et al. [188, 212] rule out the existence of
549 interdiffusion in multilayers presenting grow linearly. The inconsistencies of the model were
550 revised by Porcel et al. [214]. They introduced the concept of the restructuring inner
551 compartment which is a region of the multilayer where the polymer mobility is hindered due to
552 its high density. The formation of this zone leads to a situation in which the concentration of
553 polymer diffusing along the multilayer is constant irrespectively of the multilayer thickness.
554 However, this refined model was only to describe the behaviour when the molecular weight of
555 the polymers is relatively high (PLL with molecular weight around 360 kDa), with the diffusion
556 within the entire multilayer being found for smaller molecular weights (20 kDa).

557 The interdiffusion of at least one of the polyelectrolyte within the multilayers was associated by
558 Lavalle et al. [201] and Hoda and Larsson [215] with the existence of a Donnan effect along the
559 LbL film. This Donnan effect results from the mobile charges generated by the *in* and *out*
560 diffusion of the polyelectrolyte chains, which leads to an excess of charge within the multilayer,
561 with the interdiffusion occurring until such charge excess is completely compensated. However,
562 this framework does not provide a satisfactory explanation of the transition from linear to non-
563 linear growth occurring in some multilayers due to changes of the conditions used for the
564 assembly of the layers, e.g. (PDADMAC – PSS)_n, [107, 187, 216].

565 The existence of mobility of the polyelectrolyte chains within the whole multilayers proposed
566 by Elbert et al. [7], independently of the growth mechanism of the multilayers, was demonstrated
567 by Guzman et al. [184] from a rigorous analysis of the adsorption kinetics of the layers, which

568 has evidenced that the interdiffusion is not limited to non-linear growth materials. This suggests
569 that the differences in the multilayer roughness can contribute to the emergence of two different
570 types of growth as was evidenced for (PDADMAC – PSS)_n multilayers [187], and contradicts
571 the conclusions obtained by Lavallo et al. [189]. However, the latter study neglects the impact
572 of the specific chemical nature of the assembled polyelectrolytes, already discussed in the work
573 by Elbert et al. [7], when the comparison between linear and non-linear growth multilayers is
574 performed.

575 The impact of the roughness as driving force for the transition from a linear to a non-linear
576 growth of the polyelectrolyte multilayers can be understood considering that the increase of the
577 multilayer roughness leads to an increase of the area available for the adsorption. This results on
578 an increase of the adsorbed amount in the successive deposition cycles, and as matter of fact on
579 a non-linear growth. On the other side, the roughness remains almost constant with the increase
580 of the deposition cycles when linear growth multilayers are concerned. The transition from linear
581 to non-linear growth may be ascribed to the different conformation of the adsorbed polymer
582 chains [184, 187, 191, 216, 217]. The impact of the roughness in the growth of polyelectrolyte
583 multilayers is compatible with the results by Haynie et al. [218] in which the emergence of a
584 non-linear growth is the result of the propagation, growth and coalescence of dendritic or isolated
585 structures, which leads to the increase on the roughness of the films. The formation of
586 heterogeneous structure during the growth leads to non-linear dependences of the thickness on
587 the number of layers because the size of the deposited material results in the increase of the area
588 available for the deposition. The transition between the region of heterogeneous growth to that
589 where a homogenous growth is found may be explained as result of sterical limitations for the
590 polyelectrolyte chains, leading to a constant number of binding sites [219]. This agrees with the
591 results by Hernández-Montelongo et al. [202] using fractal analysis on Atomic Force
592 Microscopy images. They found that the assembly of linear growth (CHI-HA)_n multilayers
593 follow a pathway based on the aggregation of the molecules followed by their rearrangement,
594 whereas those multilayers presenting non-linear growth follow an assembly governed by a
595 diffusion limited aggregation. This process results in the formation of aggregates due to diffusion
596 gradients, with depleted zones remaining in the layer, which result in the formation of rough
597 multilayers with irregular surfaces. On the contrary, linear growth multilayers present a smoother
598 and regular surface. It is worth noting that the existence of region with heterogeneous growth
599 was also observed by Picart et al. [188] during the initial stages of the deposition of (PLL-HA)_n
600 multilayers, even though they neglect its impact on the emergence of the non-linear growth of

601 the multilayers. It is worth mentioning that the formation and growth of such heterogeneities
602 within the polyelectrolyte multilayer do not limit the interdiffusion to non-linear multilayers.

603 The above described dependences of the adsorbed amount on the number of bilayers are the most
604 commonly found in polyelectrolyte multilayers. However, it has been reported more exotic
605 growth dependences on specific polyelectrolyte multilayers, e.g. multilayers of a short
606 polyanion, poly(sodium phosphate), and PAH. Such exotic supramolecular films follow a growth
607 mechanism which violate most of the rules driving the assembly of LbL polyelectrolyte films
608 [220, 221], e.g. the multilayers growth without the typical charge inversion expected in
609 polyelectrolyte multilayers and it presents growth instabilities.

610 It is clear that the explanation of the possible origin of the two growth mechanisms in
611 polyelectrolyte multilayers remains far from clear. However, different studies suggest that the
612 interdiffusion of the polyelectrolyte chains within the multilayers cannot be considered the
613 distinctive signature for the transition between linear to non-linear growth, with such
614 interdiffusion appearing independently on the type of growth appearing on the multilayers. On
615 the other side, the roughness model may be suitable to explain deviations from a linear growth
616 only during the deposition of the first few layers. Thus, it may be assumed that the origin of the
617 specific growth mechanism of polyelectrolyte multilayers can be only understood from a careful
618 examination of the specific characteristics of the assembled polyelectrolytes and their
619 conformations, the conditions used for the assembly of the multilayers and the interactions
620 involved in the assembly process.

621 **3.2. Charge compensation and charge overcompensation: driving the assembly of** 622 **multilayers**

623 The use of charged compounds in the formation of LbL makes it necessary to consider the
624 important role of the electrostatic interactions between the polyelectrolyte adsorbed in adjacent
625 layers as driving force of the assembly. However, the complete understanding of the assembly
626 process requires a careful examination of the complex interplay between the different
627 interactions involved: polyelectrolyte – polyelectrolyte, polyelectrolyte – solvent and
628 polyelectrolyte – template [111, 222]. The understanding of these interactions makes it necessary
629 to consider the impact of two different aspects on the assembly: (i) quality of the solvent for the
630 polyelectrolytes (ionic strength, pH or temperature), and (ii) competence between electrostatic
631 and entropic factor [187, 216].

632 It is commonly accepted that the deposition of charged polymers or particles onto oppositely
633 charged surfaces is driven for a charge inversion phenomenon, i.e. the deposition of layer is not
634 stopped when the neutralization of the charge of the surface is reached, with the adsorption
635 proceeding until a certain degree of opposite charge appears on the surface in accordance to
636 the Surface Force Measurements by Berndt et al. [223]. This phenomenon can be understood
637 considering that the adsorption of a polyelectrolyte monolayer onto a surface bearing opposite
638 charges does not results initially on the neutralization of the surface due to steric factors, and
639 hence it is necessary the presence of additional charges chains to ensure the neutralization of the
640 uncompensated charges of the substrate. This leads to the charge inversion and to the formation
641 of layers with charged loops and tails protruding to the solution, which overcompensates the
642 charge of the initial surface and hinders the adsorption of additional molecules as result of the
643 repulsive electrostatic interaction (the LbL assembly of polyelectrolyte layers is an
644 electrostatically self-limited process). The immersion of the surface decorated with a
645 polyelectrolyte layer into a solution containing a polyelectrolyte bearing the opposite charge
646 allows the deposition of a new polyelectrolyte layer following a similar pathway to that described
647 for the previous layer, with the charge reversion, i.e. the overcompensation of the charge of
648 the previous layer enabling the alternate deposition of layers of building blocks with opposite
649 charge [51, 88, 187, 224]. It is worth mentioning that even though the charge inversion
650 phenomena may appear counterintuitive, it is essential for the electrostatic self-assembly of LbL
651 films [111], and for many other processes with interest for materials science and biology [225].

652 The overcompensation during the deposition of LbL films has been commonly studied
653 for multilayers deposited onto macroscopic substrates and onto colloidal templates in
654 term of different experimental parameters which provide information related to the charge
655 of the surface: surface potential (measured using a Kelvin probe), streaming potential or
656 the zeta potential (ζ potential, obtained from electrophoretic mobility measurements) [51,
657 88, 107, 111, 175, 185, 187, 188, 226, 227]. This type of measurements shows the
658 switching of the surface charge between positive and negative values with the alternate
659 deposition of polycation and polyanion layers, respectively. Figure 6 shows the changes
660 of the value of the ζ potential for (PAH-PSS)_n multilayers deposited onto silica colloidal
661 particles (1 μ m). The impact of the overcompensation is clear with the ζ -potential
662 oscillating between values around (30 ± 10) mV, when the adsorption of polycation layers is
663 concerned, and (-40 ± 10) mV after the deposition of PSS layers. This agrees with the assymmetric
664 growth of polyelectrolyte multilayers suggested by Ghostine et al. [228], which involves a

665 different degree of charge overcompensation depending on the nature of the deposited layer. The
666 overcompensation is maximum at the surface of the layers, and is expected to decay
667 exponentially with the penetration toward the inner region of the multilayers [107, 111].

668 The degree of charge inversion occurring upon the deposition of polyelectrolyte layers is
669 self-limiting by the specific pair of assembled polyelectrolytes, without any significant
670 impact of the conditions used for the assembly (ionic strength, pH) on the maximum degree
671 of charge inversion reached [187, 216]. However, the extension of the overcompensation within
672 the layer thickness depends on the growth mechanism and the fuzziness of the obtained
673 multilayer: (i) multilayers exhibiting non-linear growth present overcompensation throughout
674 the entire layer [189], and (ii) multilayers exhibiting linear growth present overcompensation
675 which is almost limited to the layer surface [23].

676
677 Figure 6. Change of the ζ potential with the alternate deposition of PAH and PSS layers
678 onto silica microparticles ($1 \mu\text{m}$) from polyelectrolyte solutions with concentration 1
679 mg/mL and ionic strength fixed in 10 mM. Notice that $N = 0$ corresponds to the
680 microparticles, $N=1, 2, 3$ and 4 correspond to the deposition of PSS layers, and $N= 0.5,$
681 $1.5, 2.5$ and 3.5 correspond to the deposition of PDADMAC layers.

682
683 The existence of overcompensation is correlated with an excess of polymer charges which are
684 not paired with those in the adjacent layer. The existence of such charge excess makes the
685 multilayer unstable, with its stability requiring the fulfillment of the electro-neutrality boundary
686 condition [107, 229], i.e. it is needed to introduce a contribution enabling to counter-balance of
687 the charge excess associated with the assembly of the polyelectrolyte layers and ensuring a zero

688 net charge at the macroscopic scale (beyond the Debye length). This is only possible considering
689 the incorporation of small ions which compensate the charge excess associated with unpaired
690 segments of the polyelectrolyte chains [118, 187, 230]. The possible incorporation of such small
691 ions makes it mandatory to examine the mechanism driving the charge compensation, the so-
692 called compensation mechanisms. These are required because the equilibria between the
693 different charges species appear coupled, i.e. the entrance of a cationic specie into the multilayer
694 only can occur coupled to the entrance of an anion or the creation of a negative charge within
695 the multilayer, and vice versa [231-233].

696 It is accepted the existence of two different mechanisms for the compensation of charge in
697 polyelectrolyte multilayer: (i) intrinsic, and (ii) extrinsic [229]. The former mechanism (intrinsic)
698 involves the absence of polymer charge excesses during the LbL assembly, i.e. the charges of
699 the polyelectrolyte deposited in one layer are directly compensated by the charges of the
700 polyelectrolyte adsorbed in the adjacent layer, which results in the formation of multilayers with
701 stoichiometry 1:1 (polycation:polyanion). This results in the highest level of ionic cross-linking
702 that can be expected for the assembly of polyelectrolyte multilayers. The formation of
703 intrinsically compensated multilayers requires the release of a large amount of counterions
704 (condensed counterions to the polyelectrolyte chains) from the polymeric film to the solution
705 which decreases the average free energy of the system due to the important contribution of the
706 entropy increase associated with the release of counterions. Thus, the entropy gain associated
707 with the release of the counterions becomes the driving force of the assembly of intrinsically
708 compensated LbL films. On the other side, those systems where an extrinsic compensation is
709 found need of the presence of counterions to ensure the electroneutrality of the multilayers,
710 which results in the formation of multi-layered structures with a broad range of possible
711 stoichiometries. Thus, the retention of counterions within the multilayer structure reduces the
712 impact of the entropy on the assembly of extrinsically compensated LbL films. Figure 7 shows
713 a schematic picture describing the distribution of polyelectrolytes and counterions in both types
714 of compensation mechanisms.

715

716 Figure 7. Scheme of the expected configuration of polyelectrolyte layers and counterions in
 717 intrinsically and extrinsically compensated polyelectrolyte multilayers. Reproduced from Ref.
 718 [107], Copyright (2009), with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry.

719

720 The extrinsic compensation is the most frequent in polyelectrolyte multilayers [49-51, 107, 111,
 721 118], with the intrinsic one being limited to the assembly of highly charged polyelectrolytes
 722 [107, 228, 234]. However, it is not possible to define any general rule allowing a prediction of
 723 the type of compensation expected for a specific multilayer. This is because the compensation
 724 mechanism depends on both the pair of assembled polyelectrolytes and the assembly conditions
 725 [49-51, 89, 107, 111, 118]. The ability of tuning the compensation mechanism, by changing the
 726 conditions in which the assembly is done, plays a very important role in the control of the final
 727 structure and physico-chemical properties of the LbL films [107, 111, 187]. The ionic strength
 728 of the solution is probably the most important parameter impacting on the compensation
 729 mechanism of LbL films. This is because it modify the ionic equilibrium, and as a matter of fact
 730 the effective charge density of the polyelectrolyte due to the ionic condensation phenoma [228].
 731 The effect of the ionic strength on the charge compensation mechanism of (PDADMAC - PSS)_n
 732 multilayers was demonstrated by Schlenoff and Dubas [111]. They were able to switch the
 733 multilayers from a mainly intrinsic-like compensation mechanism to an extrinsic one. This
 734 transition may be explained in terms of the role of the entropy in the assembly [107, 187]. Thus,
 735 the assembly of multilayers from solutions with low ionic strength occurs upon the release of
 736 most of the counterions to the solution, and thus an important entropy gain should be expected.
 737 On the other side, the increase of the ionic strength leads to a situation in which the release of
 738 counterions is less important, and the entropy gain does not play a significant role on the
 739 assembly. This is rationalized considering that the overall concentration of ions in the bulk is
 740 relatively high, and the release of additional counterions does not affect significantly to the
 741 energetic landscape of the system (the impact of the counterions release on the entropy of the

742 system is rather low). Therefore, most of the counterions remain trapped within the multilayer,
743 with such multilayers having a lacked ionic pairing between the charged groups of
744 polyelectrolyte chains forming adjacent layers. Figure 8 shows the impact of the ionic strength
745 on the compensation mechanism of (PDADMAC-PSS)_n multilayers in terms of the dependence
746 of monomer density, $\rho_{monomer}$, for PDADMAC and PSS layers obtained ellipsometry on the ionic
747 strength (I). The higher values of the density of PDADMAC monomers in comparison to that
748 corresponding to PSS monomer is a clear signature of the extrinsic compensation. Furthermore,
749 this increase of the density difference with the ionic strength give an indication of the transition
750 from an almost intrinsic compensation to a clearly extrinsic compensation for the highest values
751 of the ionic strength.

752 The different values obtained for the monomer densities in polycation and polyanion layers may
753 be explained considering that the charge compensation present an asymmetric character, i.e. the
754 degree of extrinsic compensation in (PDADMAC - PSS)_n multilayer is defined by the nature of
755 the capping layer [107, 235]. Therefore, the higher monomer density of PDADMAC monomers
756 leads to a situation in which the charge excess is expected to be significantly higher in
757 PDADMAC-capped films than in PSS-capped one, and consequently an extrinsic compensation
758 should be expected for PDADMAC layers, whereas a mostly intrinsic compensation appears for
759 PSS layers. These differences on the compensation mechanism as function of the specific
760 chemistry of polycation and polyanion results in important differences on the structure of the
761 adsorbed layers. Thus, the differences on the distribution profile of counterions within the
762 multilayers modify the osmotic stress and affect the layer structure, with the formation of
763 PDADMAC layers with a higher hydration and swelling than PSS one. This results in higher
764 roughness for PDADMAC-capped films than for PSS-terminated one [107, 236] (see inset
765 Figure 8). The above discussion allows inferring that the internal charge balance in
766 polyelectrolyte multilayers results from the combination of extrinsic sites
767 (polyelectrolyte/counterion pairing) and intrinsic one (pairing between oppositely charged
768 polyelectrolytes) as is schematized in Figure 9.

769

770 Figure 8. Surface density of monomer, ρ_{monomer} , for polyanion and polycation layers in
 771 $(\text{PDADMAC} - \text{PSS})_n$ multilayers as function of the ionic strengths. The differences between the
 772 PDADMAC and PSS densities are a signature of an extrinsic-like compensation. Adapted from
 773 Ref. [107], Copyright (2009), with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry. The inset
 774 represents the assymetrical compensation in polyelectrolyte multilayers as function of the nature
 775 of the last deposited layer. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [235]. Copyright (2012)
 776 American Chemical Society.

777

778 Figure 9. Scheme showing the general internal charge balance in polyelectrolyte multilayers.
 779 Reprinted from Ref. [228]. Copyright (2013) American Chemical Society

780

781 It should be expected a very different role of the enthalpy and entropy on the film assembly
 782 depending on the specific nature of the multilayers [219]. A strongly exothermic complexation

783 is expected for multilayers presenting linear growth as (PDADMAC-PSS)_n films obtained at low
784 ionic strengths, whereas the complexation appears as endothermic for non-linear growth
785 multilayers as (PDADMAC-PSS)_n obtained at high ionic strengths [107]. Thus, assuming the
786 common definition for the change of Gibbs energy of the system $\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S$, it should be
787 expected a a favourable role of both enthalpy ΔH (negative as result of the ionic pairing) and
788 entropy ΔS (positive as result of the release of counterions) in linear growth multilayers, whereas
789 for non-linear growth multilayers, even the entropic contribution continues being positive, the
790 impact of the enthalpy is detrimental for the assembly due to its positive values. Thus, the role
791 of the entropy and enthalpy must be considered counteractive for the assembly process [218,
792 237].

793 It should be expected that any variable affecting the ionic equilibrium, and not only the ionic
794 strength, of the polyelectrolytes may modify the compensation mechanism (polyelectrolyte
795 charge density, pH and solvent quality) [49, 51, 231, 238, 239]. It is worth mentioning that the
796 ionic equilibrium is not the only contribution affecting to the overall entropy of the assembly
797 process, with the entropy associated with the release and reorientation of hydration water [240-
798 242], and the entropy penalty associated with the reduction of the degrees of freedom of the
799 molecules as result to their attachment to the surface playing also a certain role [114, 243]. The
800 latter contribution presents commonly an unfavourable effect on the assembly process of LbL.
801 However, its impact, in most of the systems, is smaller than that of the other contributions,
802 allowing one to neglect its role [244].

803 The importance role of the entropy in the assembly of polyelectrolyte multilayers could be
804 summarised in three main reasons: (i) charge inversion has associated a high enthalpic penalty,
805 thus an adsorption driven only by enthalpy cannot continue proceed beyond the zero net surface
806 charge point, i.e. the compensation conditions. Therefore, the contribution of non-electrostatic
807 interactions to the LbL assembly of polyelectrolytes ensures that the process can proceed beyond
808 the charge compensation threshold; (ii) electrostatic interactions do not differ between intrinsic
809 (compensation by ionic pairing) and extrinsic compensations (compensation by counterions
810 condensation); and (iii) the possibility of building multilayers with materials presenting a
811 reduced charge density or under conditions where the electrostatic interaction is more or less
812 screened, e.g. high ionic strength [51, 107, 229, 245-249]. It is worth mentioning that the impact
813 of the electrostatic and non-electrostatic contributions on the assembly of polyelectrolyte
814 multilayers remains controvert and deserves future studies [6, 249]. The understanding of the
815 role of the different contributions to the assembly presents a particular important because there

816 are some cases in which a high charge density of the building blocks does not ensure the
817 formation of multilayers, e.g. the assembly of poly(N-ethyl-4-vinylpyridinium bromide) and
818 PMAA at pH 8.4 results in the formation of inter-polyelectrolyte complexes, even though the
819 used polymer present a high charge density. The same occurs for the pair or that of PMAA and
820 lysozyme at the same pH where both the building blocks have also a high charge density [250].

821 **3.3. Adsorption kinetics of polyelectrolyte layers in LbL multilayers**

822 The adsorption kinetics of polyelectrolyte layers in polyelectrolyte multilayers is probably
823 accounted among the less explored aspects. However, several studies have shown that the
824 understanding of the properties and structure of LbL materials requires a critical examination of
825 the time-scales involved in the adsorption processes of the layers [107, 184, 191, 229]. This is
826 particularly important because the stratification appearing in many polyelectrolyte multilayers
827 may be considered the result of an arrested adsorption, in which the structure is reminiscent of a
828 freezing at an intermediate state far from the steady state conditions [105, 106, 251]. This may
829 be rationalized considering the long time requires for the reorganization of the polyelectrolyte
830 chains within the multilayer structure [231]. Thus, the better stratification found for multilayers
831 assembled using methodologies involving low contact time between the solution and the
832 surface/multilayer, such spin-coating or spraying, than for those obtained using common dipping
833 may be explained considering an arrest of the reorganization of the polyelectrolyte chains [124,
834 138].

835 The complex interplay of interactions involving polyelectrolyte, substrate and solvent determine
836 the adsorption and growth of LbL films, and, in particular, the adsorption kinetics [113].
837 Polyelectrolytes adsorption is an almost a quasi-irreversible process, i.e. once a polyelectrolyte
838 chain is attached to the surface it remains trapped, which can be rationalized considering that the
839 adsorption process of a polymeric chain to a surface results from a multi-segment binding, i.e.
840 more than one monomers attach to the surface. Thus, the desorption of an adsorbed chain requires
841 that all the segment can be unbound simultaneously, which is difficult because during the
842 desorption process, additional polymeric segment can attach to the surface, making almost
843 impossible the desorption of the entire chain from the surface, at least within experimental
844 accessible time-scales [252, 253]. The above picture provides an explanation to the impossibility
845 of washing out a polyelectrolyte layer from the substrate upon their exposure to a solution
846 containing a polyelectrolyte bearing the opposite charge, i.e. a counter-polyelectrolyte [107].

847 Most of the studies dealing with the adsorption kinetics of layers on LbL multilayers have
848 evidenced the existence of at least two well-differentiated steps [51, 107, 184, 191, 254]. This
849 type of kinetics can be described according to the Raposo-Avrami's adsorption model which
850 provide a description of the time dependence of the surface concentration $\Gamma(t)$ as follows [255-
851 257],

$$852 \quad \Gamma(t) = A_1(1 - e^{-t/\tau_1}) + A_2(1 - e^{-t/\tau_2})^n, \quad (1)$$

853 with A_1 and A_2 being the amplitudes for the fast and slow adsorption steps, respectively and τ_1
854 and τ_2 the corresponding characteristic times. It is worth noting that the second term accounts for
855 any reorganization process of the polymer chain after its adsorption, including both the diffusion
856 within the multilayer structure and the motion of the polymer molecule in the surface plane,
857 generally to ensure the compensation of all surface charges, with the latter being probably
858 associated with displacements of the polymer chains on localized and uncorrelated short scales
859 (inchworm-like motion) [109, 258]. The reorganization of the polymers chains is modeled in
860 terms of an expression reminiscent of the Avrami's model, which is commonly applied to the
861 description of the kinetic of polymer crystallization [259-261]. The exponent of the Avrami's
862 term n assumes values close to 1 for almost all the polyelectrolyte multilayers which allows one
863 to rewrite Equation (1) in terms of the maximum value of the surface concentration, Γ_∞ ,

$$864 \quad \Gamma_\infty = A_1 + A_2 \quad (2)$$

$$865 \quad \Gamma = \Gamma_\infty - A_1 e^{-t/\tau_1} - A_2 e^{-t/\tau_2} \quad (3)$$

866 The adsorption of a single polyelectrolyte layer during the fabrication of a LbL films involved
867 two kinetic appearing in well-separated time scales: (i) a first fast nucleation of polyelectrolyte
868 domains (generally below 5 minutes), and (ii) slow reorganization of the polymer chains within
869 the multilayer (from several minutes to hours) [262]. The first step can be considered a diffusion-
870 controlled process coupled to the adsorption of the polymer through an electrostatic or steric
871 barrier [253, 263], whereas the second step involves all the reorganization steps driving the
872 adsorption to the stationary state, including both in plane reorganizations of the polymeric chains
873 and the interdiffusion along the whole multilayer structure [116, 254]. Figure 10 shows for the
874 sake of example the adsorption kinetics of PDADMAC layer on a (PDADMAC - PSS)_n film,
875 and the discrimination of the two processes involved in the assembly process.

876 The results shown in Figure 10 evidence the validity of the above discussed model for providing
877 an appropriate description of the adsorption kinetics. It is worth mentioning that the first
878 adsorption step generally takes the system up to the 60 - 80 % of the value of Γ corresponding
879 to the steady state [49, 51, 89, 107]. The adsorption of most of the polyelectrolyte multilayers
880 presents a characteristic time for the first process τ_1 almost independent on the number of layers
881 [51, 89]. However, the values of τ_1 are affected by the variables that modify the assembly process
882 (pH, ionic strength, T, etc.) in agreement with the computer simulations by Cohen-Stuart [253].
883 On the other side, τ_2 can present complex dependences on the number of layers, making it
884 difficult to predict the dependence for a specific multilayer [112, 116, 191]. τ_2 is related to in
885 plane reorganizations of the polymer chains, i.e. processes occurring at the multilayer surface,
886 for systems such as (PAH - PSS)_n or (PDMAEMA - PSS)_n multilayers, with the characteristic
887 time remaining almost constant with the number of layers [49, 116, 191]. However, other
888 systems, including (PDADMAC - PSS)_n or (CHI - PAA)_n multilayers, present increasing τ_2
889 values with the multilayer thickness. This suggests that the reorganization process can account
890 for both the interdiffusion of the polymer within the multilayer tri-dimensional structure and
891 the in plane reorganization process [51, 116, 191]. The above picture agrees with the three stage
892 model proposed for Lane et al. [254] for the adsorption of polyelectrolyte layers on multilayers
893 formed by PSS and poly[1-[4[(3-carboxy-4-hydroxyphenylazo)benzenesulfonamido]-1,2-
894 ethanediyl sodium salt]. This model includes: (i) transport of the polymer from the solution to
895 the surface, (ii) in plane reorganization of the adsorbed chains, and (iii) interdiffusion of polymer
896 chains within the multilayer structure. Figure 11 presents a scheme including the different
897 processes which can be involved in the adsorption of polyelectrolyte on a multilayer.

898

899 Figure 10. Adsorption kinetics, and example of their analysis, for the adsorption of PDADMAC
 900 layer on a $(\text{PDADMAC} - \text{PSS})_n$ film. (a) Adsorption kinetics. The solid line shows the best fit to
 901 Equation (3), with the two exponential steps being evidenced: (---) first fast step and (····) second
 902 slow step. (b) Long time behavior of the adsorption kinetics plotted as $\ln(\Gamma_{\infty} - \Gamma)$ vs. time, with
 903 the solid line representing the fit to a straight line. (c) Short time behavior of the adsorption
 904 kinetics plotted as $\ln(\Gamma_{\infty} - \Gamma - A_2 e^{-t/\tau^2})$ vs. time, with the fit evidenced by a solid line. Adapted from
 905 Ref. [191], Copyright (2011), with permission from Elsevier.

906

907 It is worth noting that a close look on the dependences of the adsorption times on the number of
 908 layers provides a valuable information on the determination of the possible role of the
 909 interdiffusion of the polyelectrolyte chains [116, 191], with the assembly conditions and the
 910 chemical nature of the polyelectrolyte forming the multilayer modifying significantly the
 911 adsorption kinetics [49-51, 116].

912

913 Figure 11. Scheme of the different processes involved in the adsorption of polyelectrolyte on
 914 LbL multilayers. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [116]. Copyright (2012) American
 915 Chemical Society.

916

917 3.4. Internal structure of polyelectrolyte multilayers

918 The internal structure of polyelectrolyte multilayers plays an essential role on the physico-
 919 chemical properties of the assembled systems, which makes it necessary a careful control over
 920 the different variables affecting the assembly process because they may modify the final
 921 structure of the films.

922 The main question to solve, when the internal structure of polyelectrolyte multilayers is
 923 concerned, is the extension of their lamellar order, i.e. whether consecutive layers are truly
 924 independent layers to enable the definition of the LbL multilayer as stratified materials [124,
 925 138, 191]. This has been found to be strongly dependent on the nature of the assembled
 926 polyelectrolytes, the conditions used for the assembly of the films, and the protocol of fabrication
 927 (contact time and deposition method) [11, 124, 138, 191]. The general description of
 928 polyelectrolyte multilayers is based in a division of the tridimensional structure of the film into
 929 three different zones (three zone model), with a progressive transition on the multilayer structure
 930 between adjacent zones [185, 264]. The zone I corresponds to the region closest to the substrate,
 931 and it is the first region of the multilayer which is formed during the assembly of the LbL
 932 material. This regions is characterized by the alignment of the polyelectrolyte chains along the

933 substrate surface, with its thickness remaining constant during the whole assembly process.
934 Furthermore, the mobility of polyelectrolytes adsorbed in this region is very limited. The zone
935 II is formed after the zone I, and presents an increasingly thickness during the assembly process.
936 The structure of zone II resembles to that found for inter-polyelectrolyte complexes in solution
937 [229, 264]. The outer region of the multilayer is the zone III, which maintains a constant
938 thickness within the entire fabrication process of the multilayer, and presents a structure
939 reminiscent to that what is expected for a free polyelectrolyte in solution [258, 265]. The three
940 zone model was recently revisited by Singh et al. [266]. They found in $(PEI-PSS)_n$ multilayers
941 different structural regions: (i) an inhomogeneous region near to the substrate which is associated
942 with the influence of the interactions between the surface and the polyelectrolyte, and (ii) a
943 homogeneous region after the deposition of a certain number of layers. Figure 12 shows a scheme
944 of the evolution of the different zones with the multilayer growth.

945
946 Figure 12. Scheme representing the three zone model of the multilayer structure, and its
947 evolution with the increase of the number of layers. Adapted from Ref. [264], Copyright (2017),
948 with permission from Elsevier.

949
950 The above picture provides a general perspective of the internal structure of polyelectrolyte
951 multilayers. However, a more detailed structural characterization of this type of materials has
952 been obtained using reflectivity technique, mainly neutron reflectometry (NR) and X-Ray
953 reflectometry (XRR), and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) [105-107, 187, 191]. The
954 first studies dealing with the structural characterization of polyelectrolyte multilayers paid
955 attention to $(PAH - PSS)_n$ multilayers by combining NR and XRR [105, 106]. They performed
956 a careful examination of the stratification of the films by NR experiments, introducing for such
957 purpose, different sequences of layers where each certain number of layers the polyanion (PSS)

958 was replaced by a layer of deuterated PSS (d-PSS). These experiments showed that even a certain
959 degree of stratification can appear in the multilayers, the formation of a true lamellar structure
960 in which independent layers may be found is far to be the real situation multilayers, existing a
961 certain degree of interdigitation between the layers, which is related to the distance to the
962 substrate, and generally is propagated along three or more bilayers [105, 106, 267]. Furthermore,
963 they found that the three zone model provided an appropriate description for the correlations
964 existing between the stratification degree of the multilayer and the thickness of the multilayer,
965 and an increase of the roughness with the number of layers until reaching an stationary value as
966 result of the densification occurring during the assembly process [105, 106]. The latter finding
967 is just the opposite to that what happens for (PDADMAC-PSS)_n multilayers, which present a
968 decrease on their roughness as the growing process proceeds [268]. The difference in the
969 roughness may be explained considering the different mechanism involved in the assembly of
970 the polyelectrolyte layers in (PAH - PSS)_n and (PDADMAC - PSS)_n systems, with the
971 interdiffusion within the film playing an important role in the latter case [184, 191], which allows
972 one to distinguish between two different types of roughness: (i) topological roughness as that
973 appearing in (PAH - PSS)_n multilayers [105, 106], and (ii) roughness associated with the
974 assembly process as that found in (PDADMAC - PSS)_n multilayers [268]. It is worth mentioning
975 that analogous differences has been reported by Guzmán et al. [191].

976 The differences between (PAH - PSS)_n and (PDADMAC - PSS)_n multilayers go beyond the
977 impact of the assembling processes on the roughness of the films [105-107, 184, 187, 191] as
978 was pointed out by Guzmán et al. [107, 187, 191]. They showed, combining NR, XRR and XPS,
979 that the stratification of (PDADMAC-PSS)_n was completely absent, independently of the
980 assembling conditions used for the building of the multilayers, which may be explained
981 considering the differences of the times used for the layer assembly, with longer time used for
982 the assembly of (PDADMAC-PSS)_n multilayer that for (PAH - PSS)_n one (adsorption of the
983 layers to reach the steady state conditions, around 1 hour [107], vs. adsorption during 15 – 20
984 minutes [105, 106]). This suggest that the structure of polyelectrolyte multilayers may be
985 affected by a dynamic constrain, which favors the formation of films with a partial stratification
986 as result of an arrested adsorption as was predicted by Panchagnula et al. [251] on the basis of
987 molecular dynamics simulations. It is worth mentioning that deepening in the impact of the time
988 on the stratification of LbL layer, Guzmán et al. [191] found that the stratification of LbL film
989 depends on the adsorption kinetics of the layers, with (PDADMAC - PSS)_n multilayers where
990 the interdiffusion presents a central role on the assembly no showing any signature of

991 stratification, whereas (PAH - PSS)_n multilayers evidence a time dependent stratification [191].
992 The temporal evolution of the structure of the multilayers has been also observed by Ge et al.
993 [269] using Vibrational Sum Frequency Generation Spectroscopy. The impact of the time used
994 for the layer assembly on the lamellar order of polyelectrolyte multilayers has been recently
995 confirmed by Selin et al. [270]. They found that multilayers of poly(methacrylic acid) (PMAA)
996 as polyanion and quaternized poly(2-(dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate) (QPC) as
997 polycation present an enhanced intermixing of the layers as the adsorption time increases. This
998 was evidenced from the evolution of the neutron scattering length density profiles with the
999 adsorption time: (i) short adsorption times result in a layer intermixing which occurs only on the
1000 most external layers, and (ii) long adsorption times result in a intermixing within the entire
1001 multilayers. Therefore, the adsorption time can be identified as the driving force leading to the
1002 increase of the thickness of the region within the intermixing occurs. A recent study has shown
1003 that the thermal annealing can be used for the destruction of the lamellar structure [271]. This is
1004 the result of two simultaneous process which impact on different regions of the film: (i)
1005 densification, and (ii) degradation. The impact of the annealing with salt on the structure of
1006 (PDADMAC - PSS)_n multilayers was found to be similar to the thermal annealing [272]. The
1007 absence of a true stratification in polyelectrolyte LbL materials makes it is necessary to redefine
1008 this type of systems as solid supported inter-polyelectrolyte complexes, existing two types: (i)
1009 partially stratified, and (ii) non-stratified[273].

1010 Many technological fields based on LbL materials require stratified systems. This can be solved
1011 using the approach proposed by Gilbert et al. [274]. They design a methodology enabling the
1012 fabrication of stratified polyelectrolyte multilayers, including, in the multi-layered structure of
1013 the film, different single layers which blocks the interdiffusion of the other polymers. It is worth
1014 mentioning that the absence of such layers favours the formation of homogeneously
1015 interdigitated films.

1016

1017 **4. Controlling the assembly of Layer-by-Layer multilayers: parameter modifying the** 1018 **assembly**

1019 The above discussion evidenced that the LbL method is not a true methodology for coating
1020 fabrication, with this methodology being a self-limiting adsorption process which drives the
1021 formation inter-polyelectrolyte complexes supported, in most of the cases, by a template. The
1022 control of the properties and structure of such materials requires a careful examination of the

1023 bath conditions (pH, added salt, concentration), and the properties of the building blocks and
1024 templates [113, 275].

1025 **4.1. Physico-chemical properties of the template**

1026 The discussion of Section 2 evidenced that that polyelectrolyte multilayers may be assembled in
1027 a broad range of substrates with different chemical nature, morphology and size [114]. The
1028 specific chemical nature of the surfaces, and, in particular, their surface charge density are critical
1029 parameters for the assembly of LbL materials onto its surface [11]. This is because the suitability
1030 of a specific substrate as template is correlated to the specific nature of the interactions occurring
1031 between the polyelectrolyte and the substrate. This is generally related to the
1032 hydrophilicity/phobicity characteristics of the template, its chemical nature and the density of
1033 the charged groups existing in its surface, as well as to its roughness, porosity and the presence
1034 of impurities [276]. This is because such parameters present a critical impact on the homogeneity
1035 and the stability of the obtained multi-layer films, or at least on the corresponding to the layers
1036 which interact stronger with the substrate, i.e. the first deposited layers [185, 277-281].
1037 Furthermore, the interactions between the substrate and the initially deposited layers can control
1038 the specific growth mechanism as was discussed above [182, 218, 219].

1039 **4.2. Concentration of the solutions of polyelectrolytes**

1040 The fabrication of LbL materials occurs after the exposure of the substrate to be coated to a
1041 solution containing the material to be assembled, which requires the use of solutions with a
1042 concentration high enough to enable the deposition of stable layers and to ensure the charge
1043 inversion in those systems where the electrostatic contribution is critical [184, 191, 210].
1044 Therefore, the minimum concentration required for the assembly of LbL films will depend on
1045 the solubility and charge density of the assembled blocks, and it would be expected that the
1046 increase of the concentration of the solutions beyond a certain threshold value present a rather
1047 limited impact on the assembly process [191]. Figure 13 shows the polycation concentration
1048 dependence of the thickness per bilayer of the linear growth (PDMAEMA-PSS)_n multilayers in
1049 which polycations with different charge densities are included. It is clear the increase of the
1050 thickness per bilayer with the polycation concentration up to reach a threshold concentration
1051 value.

1052 The increase of the polyelectrolyte concentration leads to the formation of thicker multilayers
1053 [49, 191]. This is rationalized considering the formation of fuzzier layers, with a higher

1054 proportion of loops and tails protruding to the solution, as result of the competence of the
 1055 polymers chains for the binding points of the surface. Furthermore, the polymer concentration
 1056 may affect significantly to the growth mechanism and the intermolecular association within the
 1057 multilayers as was evidenced by Shen et al. [282]. They showed that for (PLL-HA)_n multilayers,
 1058 the increase of the HA concentration above a threshold value (around 2 mg/mL) results in a
 1059 transition from a linear growth to a non-linear one. Guzman et al. [49] and a Garg et al. [283]
 1060 show similar dependence for (PDMAEMA-PSS)_n multilayers and for those formed by PAH and
 1061 Poly[1-(*p*-(3'-carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenylazo)benzenesulfonamide)-1,2-ethandiyl], respectively.

1062
 1063 Figure 13. Polycation concentration dependences of the average thickness per bilayer of
 1064 (PDMAEMA(*x*)-PSS)_n, where *x* indicates the weight fraction of the charged block in the
 1065 copolymer. Adapted with permission from Ref. [49]. Copyright (2010) American Chemical
 1066 Society.

1067
 1068 **4.3. Nature of the building blocks: chemistry, charge density and molecular weight**

1069 The chemical nature of the polyelectrolytes and, in particular, their charge density, together with
 1070 the assembly conditions play a central role in the control of the assembly of the LbL multilayer.
 1071 This is explained considering their impact on the complex balance of interactions existing during
 1072 the assembly process, and the ability of the assembly blocks for being assembled through
 1073 electrostatic interactions or any other specific interactions. A careful examination of the role of
 1074 the interactions is essential for tuning the thickness, structure and properties of the LbL

1075 multilayers [113, 212]. This is especially important, when the deposition of the initially deposited
1076 layers is concerned because the attachment of such first layers to the substrates is critical on the
1077 stability of the obtained multi-layered structure [113].

1078 The first aspect to consider in relation to the impact of the chemical nature of the building blocks
1079 is the role of the hydrophilic/hydrophobic balance of the polymers. This is because it determines
1080 both the interactions between the polyelectrolyte and the swelling degree of the layers [284]. It
1081 has been demonstrated that the thickness of the layers increases with the hydrophobicity of the
1082 polyelectrolytes, e.g. $(\text{PDADMAC} + \text{PAMS})_n$ (with PAMS being poly(acrylamidesulfonic acid))
1083 $< (\text{PAH} + \text{PSS})_n < (\text{PDADMAC} + \text{PSS})_n$ [285]. This is explained considering the penalty
1084 associated with the solvation of the chains [118]. Furthermore, the poorer solubility of
1085 hydrophobic blocks in polar solvents, as water, is associated with the depletion of the material
1086 from the solution, which contributes to its deposition on the multilayer [50, 240, 243, 263, 286].
1087 The flexibility of the polymer chains also impact decisively on the assembly of LbL films
1088 because it modifies the conformation of the layers, and as matter of fact the interaction between
1089 the chains in solution and the layers [113, 116, 191, 212].

1090 The charge density of the building blocks is also an important parameter on the fabrication of
1091 polyelectrolyte LbL multilayers, mainly because the interactions between charges plays a very
1092 important role on the fabrication of this type of materials. Therefore, it is expected the existence
1093 of a minimum charge density threshold for enabling the building process [114, 115, 246, 287,
1094 288]. The threshold charge density is a reference state below which the formation of stable
1095 multilayers is not possible. This is explained considering that below a threshold value of the
1096 charge density, the adsorption of the polyelectrolyte is relatively weak, and thus the exposure of
1097 the adsorbed to a solution containing an oppositely charged polyelectrolyte results in a removal
1098 of the weakly bound layer, resulting in the formation of complexes into the bulk. This is favored
1099 because the enthalpy change associated with the electrostatic interaction cannot compensate the
1100 entropy gain due to the release of the weakly adsorbed polymer from the surface, yielding in the
1101 desorption of the chains [118, 175]. It is worth mentioning that the charge density threshold may
1102 be shifted by adding salt to the polyelectrolyte solutions, i.e. enhancing the role of the
1103 hydrophobic interactions [289]. The importance of the charge density of the building blocks on
1104 the assembly of polyelectrolyte multilayers was evidenced by Glinel et al. [115]. They studied
1105 multilayers between PSS and statistic copolymers of (diallyl-dimethylammonium chloride) and
1106 (N-methylformamide) with different molar ratio between the ionic and non-ionic blocks, and
1107 found three different zones for the growth of these multilayers: (i) for copolymers with the lowest

1108 charge densities (below 10%), no multilayer growth was found; (ii) for copolymers with charge
1109 densities in the 10-40% range, the thickness of the multilayers increases as the charge density of
1110 copolymers decreases, and (iii) for copolymers with charge densities above 40%, the thickness
1111 of the multilayers remains almost unchanged with the charge density of the copolymer.

1112 It is true that a minimal charge density is important for the LbL assembly because the
1113 electrostatic self-assembly of polyelectrolyte is the result of two counteracting forces: (i)
1114 electrostatic attraction between the polyelectrolyte and the oppositely charged substrate, and (ii)
1115 solubility of the polyelectrolyte. The increase of the charge density makes it less favorable the
1116 adsorption of the polyelectrolyte, which leads to a situation in which the thicker multilayers are
1117 obtained for polymers presenting a charge density between the lower charge density threshold
1118 and the maximum nominal charge density of the polyelectrolyte. The dependence of the adsorbed
1119 amount on the charge density of the polyelectrolyte can be explained as result of the balance
1120 between the above mentioned forces [288]. Therefore, the variation of the thickness for charge
1121 densities above the charge density threshold value can be understood assuming that the increase
1122 of the charge density of the copolymer drives the system from a charge-dependent “Debye
1123 Hückel” regime to a charge-independent “strong-screening” regime [115]. It is worth mentioning
1124 that the analysis of the impact of the charge density on the adsorption of polyelectrolyte also
1125 requires a careful examination of its distribution within the polymeric chain, e.g. the adsorption
1126 of block copolymers, presenting at least a strongly charge block, can be significant even for
1127 polymers with a reduced charge density (around the 10% of the number of monomers) [238].

1128 A last but not least aspect to consider on the impact of the polyelectrolyte nature on the assembly
1129 of multilayers is the role of the molecular weight of the chains in the assembly process. The high
1130 and low molecular weight concepts in polyelectrolyte multilayers should be analyzed in relation
1131 to their impact on the multilayer growth [149, 290]. In general, the assembly of low molecular
1132 weight polyelectrolytes (around 10^3 Da) leads to the stripping off of a polyelectrolyte layer upon
1133 its exposure to a polyelectrolyte of opposite charge, which hinders the multilayer growth. On the
1134 other side, the increase of the molecular mass of the assembled polyelectrolytes enhances the
1135 deposition of the multilayers. This may be easily understood considering that the adsorption-
1136 desorption is a kinetically-controlled process and the increase of the molecular weight of the
1137 adsorbing species slows down the exchange of adsorbed polymer between the multilayer and the
1138 solution. This allows concluding that the impact of the molecular weight on the multilayer
1139 growth is the result of a complicate balance between two counteracting forces: (i)
1140 thermodynamically-driven stripping resulting in the formation of inter-polyelectrolyte

1141 complexes in solution, and (ii) kinetically-driven sticking of the polymers resulting in multi-
1142 layering [149].

1143 The impact of the molecular weight of the assembled polyelectrolytes has been recently revisited
1144 by Towle et al. [117]. Their study was focused on the assembly of (PLL-PAA)_n multilayers using
1145 polyelectrolytes with a broad range of molecular weights, and they found an increase of the
1146 adsorbed amount and rigidity of the obtained films with the molecular weight of the assembled
1147 polymer. However, they also found that the specific charge density distribution and the stripping
1148 phenomena results in a non-monotonic variation of the surface roughness and the surface energy
1149 of the films.

1150 **4.4. Methodological aspects: drying, rinsing and contact time**

1151 The analysis of the role of different methodological aspects, including the contact time between
1152 the solution and the multilayer, as well as the rinsing and drying steps between the adsorption of
1153 adjacent layers, on the building of polyelectrolyte multilayers is essential.

1154 The role of the contact time on the assembly of LbL multilayers was introduced in Section 3
1155 where the impact of this aspect on the fabrication process was clearly stated. This is especially
1156 true when multilayers involving interdiffusion are concerned. The use of long adsorption times
1157 results, in most of the cases, in a weakening of the lamellar structure of the multilayers due to
1158 the internal reorganization of the polyelectrolyte chains within the tridimensional structure of the
1159 multilayer [191]. However, the use of short contact times between the solution and the multilayer
1160 results in a kinetical arrest of the interdiffusion [251], which leads to a certain degree of lamellar
1161 structure in the film [105, 106]. Thus, it is possible to assume that the stratification of the
1162 polyelectrolyte multilayers is correlated to the contact time, and hence the fabrication of stratified
1163 films makes it necessary the use of short adsorption times. This agrees with the results by
1164 Kharlampieva et al. [138] about the impact of the methodology used for the assembly of (PAH
1165 - PSS)_n multilayers on the internal structure of the multilayer. They found that the use of
1166 fabrication techniques requiring a low contact time between the solution and the multilayer (e.g.
1167 spray-assisted deposition or spin-coating: 30 – 180 seconds) results in multilayers with a better
1168 stratification than those obtained using methodologies where the contact time is long enough for
1169 enabling the interdiffusion of the polymer chains (dipping method). This scenario agrees with
1170 the better stratification reported by Félix et al. [124] for other multilayers as the contact time was
1171 reduced. Furthermore, the reduction of the contact time can allow an improvement on the

1172 homogeneity of the assembled films as result of the limitation of the polymer diffusion [146].
1173 Thus, the fabrication of LbL materials present an important kinetics control [291].

1174 The rinsing between the deposition of adjacent layers presents a key importance because it allows
1175 removing the excess of deposited materials which is adsorbed onto the surface through weak
1176 intermolecular interactions. This is especially important when the deposition of polyelectrolytes
1177 is analyzed because in absence of rinsing steps, the exposure of a multilayer capped with a
1178 polyelectrolyte to a solution of a second polyelectrolyte bearing the opposite charge can result
1179 in the formation of inter-polyelectrolyte complexes in solution (thermodynamically favored),
1180 with the precipitation of such complexes onto the multilayer distorting the structure and
1181 properties of the films [11, 292-294]. It is worth mentioning that the introduction of rinsing steps
1182 in the assembly process affects very differently to polyelectrolytes [175]. The layers of strong
1183 polyelectrolytes remain almost unaltered after their exposure to rinsing solution as result of their
1184 almost irreversible attachment through strong electrostatic interactions. On the other side, the
1185 weakness of the binding strength of layers formed by weak polyelectrolytes may result in an
1186 easier removal upon exposure to a rinsing solution [11, 295]. It is worth noting that recent studies
1187 have suggested the important role of the time used for the rinsing step to ensure a correct removal
1188 of the excess of polyelectrolyte. This is even more important when the deposition of LbL films
1189 onto heterogeneous surfaces is analyzed [291].

1190 Another methodological aspect to be considered on the assembly of LbL layers is the drying of
1191 the film between two consecutive deposition steps. Different studies have reported the essential
1192 role of the drying for tuning the structure and physico-chemical properties of polyelectrolyte
1193 multilayers [11, 262] This is because the LbL method is a wet methodology, and the drying may
1194 modify the hydration and swelling of the adsorbed layers which may modify the structural
1195 organization of the multilayer [11, 262]. These modifications may affect to the growth
1196 mechanism of the films, and even the drying of the films may hinder the adsorption of additional
1197 layers, stopping consequently the propagation of the assembly process [134]. Raposo et al. [257]
1198 pointed out that the drying between the adjacent layer was mandatory in (POMA - PVS)_n
1199 multilayers (with POMA and PVS being poly(o-methoxyaniline) and poly(vinylsulfonic acid),
1200 respectively) for ensuring an optimal growth of the films, with the methodology followed for the
1201 drying process affecting to both the multilayer structure and the properties of the obtained film.
1202 This is clear from the different structures of (PAH - PSS)_n multilayers observed for multilayers
1203 dried under ambient air and under a nitrogen stream, with the latter being more disordered [296,
1204 297]. It is worth noting that the impact of the drying on the assembly of LbL materials is strongly

1205 correlated to the assembly protocol, which may modify the stability of the films and their
1206 applicability.

1207 **4.5. Solvent polarity**

1208 Most of the films obtained by the LbL method are generally obtained from polyelectrolyte
1209 solutions in water. This is because water is a good solvent for almost all the polyelectrolyte,
1210 which is favourable for a deposition approach based on the contact of solutions containing the
1211 material to be assembled and the substrate. Furthermore, the use of water allows minimizing the
1212 toxicity associated with the use of most of the organic solvent. However, in some case can be
1213 interesting the use of organic solvents with different polarities on the assembly of LbL materials
1214 to tune the interactions and conformations of the building blocks, and as matter of fact the
1215 structure and properties of the obtained films. Among the organic solvents for controlling the
1216 assembly of LbL films can be accounted ethanol, dimethylformamide, dimethylsulfoxide or
1217 chloroform [118, 298-300]. The use of such solvents provides the bases for decreasing the role
1218 of the electrostatic interactions on the deposition, tuning the control of the assembly toward the
1219 dispersion forces and hydrogen bonds [11].

1220 It was shown that the assembly of (PDADMAC - PSS)_n multilayers from aqueous solutions
1221 including increasing ethanol weight fractions on the deposition of thicker films [239]. This may
1222 be rationalized that the decrease of the dielectric constant of the solvent associated with the
1223 addition of ethanol worsens the solubility of the polyelectrolytes because it screens the
1224 electrostatic interactions, favouring their depletion from the solution which results in an
1225 enhanced deposition. Similar results have been observed by the use of chloroform or
1226 dimethylformamide to modify the interactions involved in the assembly of (PAH - PSS)_n
1227 multilayers [299, 300]. Therefore, the worsening of the solvent quality for a specific building
1228 block may be favourable for enhancing the deposition [301-303].

1229 **4.6. Ionic strength: concentration and nature of the supporting electrolyte**

1230 The change of the ionic strength, I , of the solutions can strongly affect the complexation process
1231 between the polycations and the polyanions during the assembly of LbL films [110]. This is
1232 rationalized considering the incorporation of additional counterions to the system modifies the
1233 balance between the enthalpic and entropic contributions to the assembly process as was
1234 discussed in Section 3. Furthermore, the additional counterions screen the charges along the
1235 chains, decreasing their effective charge, and consequently the inter- and intra-chains repulsion

1236 between the polyelectrolytes that results on a conformational transition from a rod-like
 1237 conformation to a more coiled one. This results in a worsening of the solubility of the
 1238 polyelectrolyte and, in most of the cases, in an enhanced deposition and a change of the
 1239 multilayer structure [107, 110, 111]. This is clear from the results in Figure 14 where an increase
 1240 of the film thickness with the ionic strength is observed for (PDADMAC - PSS)_n and (PAH -
 1241 PSS)_n multilayers [116].

1242
 1243 Figure 14. Effect of I on the growth of (PDADMAC-PSS)_n (■) and (PAH-PSS)_n (○) multilayers
 1244 as h_{ac} (thickness obtained using a Dissipative Quartz Crystal Microbalance) vs. number of layers
 1245 at $I = 100$ mM (a) and $I = 500$ mM (b). The lines are guides for the eyes. Adapted with permission
 1246 from Ref. [116]. Copyright (2012) American Chemical Society.

1247
 1248 It is worth mentioning that there is an upper ionic strength threshold value above which the
 1249 thickness of the multilayer is not modified, and even for specific polyelectrolyte pairs the
 1250 assembly process can be completely hindered. This is explained considering a high level of
 1251 screening of the polyelectrolyte charges, which limits the adsorption of the chains via

1252 electrostatic interactions [304]. Furthermore, there are systems where a high increase of the ionic
1253 strength can result on the deconstruction of the multilayers. This is critically correlated to degree
1254 of ionic pairing occurring in the multilayers [305], which is rationalized assuming a weakening
1255 of the complexation process as result of the reduced charge density of the polyelectrolyte chains,
1256 resulting in less stable multilayers. The threshold value of salt concentration resulting in the
1257 deconstruction of the multilayers (stable-unstable) depends strongly on both the type of salt and
1258 the charge density of the polyelectrolytes [219].

1259 The above discussion evidenced that together with the salt concentration, the type of supporting
1260 electrolyte can affect decisively on the properties and growth of polyelectrolyte multilayers. This
1261 may be described in terms of the ion specific effects accounted by the Hofmeister series, which
1262 ranks the ions in terms of its ability to order or disorder the water around the molecules [306,
1263 307]. This modifies the swelling degree and hydration of the multilayers, which results in
1264 different modification of the properties and structure of the multilayers [308-310]. It is general
1265 that small ions (the so-called kosmotropic ions, water structure makers), such as F^- or Li^+ , present
1266 a weak binding to the multilayer as result of their small polarizability. Thus, they are easily
1267 excluded from the multilayer, resulting in the formation of thin films with a reduced hydration
1268 and roughness. On the other side, big ions (the so-called chaotropic ions, water structure
1269 breakers), such as I^- or Cs^+ , present a stronger binding to the multilayer due to its larger
1270 polarizability. This results in a stronger screening of the polyelectrolyte charges, i.e. a more
1271 extrinsic compensation, and consequently the polymers adopt a more coiled conformation, which
1272 result in an increase of the thickness and roughness of the obtained films [308, 311, 312].
1273 Therefore, it is possible to assume that the hydrophobicity degree of the ions modifies the
1274 thickness of the multilayers, i.e. thickness increases with hydrophobicity of the ions, with cations
1275 impacting less on the growth of polyelectrolyte multilayers than anions [307, 313]. It is worth
1276 noting that the contribution of the ionic specific effects appears for ionic strength values
1277 exceeding a threshold value (around 100 mM), with the common electrostatic interactions
1278 govern the assembly of multilayers below such threshold [311]. The analysis of the building of
1279 (PDADMAC - PSS)_n multilayers in presence of different sodium salt evidenced dependences for
1280 the thickness and roughness of the multilayers according to the following series: $Br^- > NO_3^- >$
1281 $ClO_3^- > Cl^- > BrO_3^- > HCOO^- > F^-$ [308, 309]. Figure 15 shows the dependences of the thickness
1282 on the number of layers for (PDADMAC - PSS)_n multilayers deposited from solutions containing
1283 sodium salts presenting different anions, and a scheme of association of two different counterions
1284 with the deposited polyelectrolyte layers.

1285 The effects associated with the differences on the hydrophobicity of the cations are less important
 1286 than those corresponding to the anions. However, Long et al. [313] found that multilayers the
 1287 thickness of the of (PDADMAC - PAMS)_n multilayers can be tuned using ionic salt containing
 1288 different cations during the assembly. The results show that the thickness of the multilayers
 1289 showed the following dependence on the nature of the cation: $Li^+ < Na^+ < K^+$. Similar results have
 1290 been found for (PAH-PSS)_n multilayers, where the high strength of the interaction between Cs^+
 1291 and PSS leads to the formation of unstable films [314]. Therefore, the ionic specific effects may
 1292 drive the transition between linear and non-linear growth mechanisms or instabilities on the
 1293 multilayer growth as the ion size increases [308, 311].

1294 Figure 15. (a) Dependence of the film thickness as was determined by ellipsometry on the
 1295 number of layers for (PDADMAC - PSS)_n multilayers deposited from solution containing a
 1296 concentration 0.1 M of sodium salt with different anions. Adapted with permission from Ref.
 1297 [308]. Copyright (2004) American Chemical Society. (b) Scheme representing the effect of two
 1298 counterions with very different effect on the multilayer growth. Reproduced from Ref. [113],
 1299 Copyright (2006), with permission from the PCCP Owner Societies.

1300

1301 It is worth mentioning that the Hofmeister series only provides an appropriate description on the
 1302 effect of univalent salts on the thickness, degree of swelling, and extent of layer interpenetration
 1303 of conventional polyelectrolyte multilayers [315]. The situation appears more complex when
 1304 multivalent salts are incorporated. Multivalent ions can induce the formation of intra- or
 1305 interchain bridge of the polyelectrolyte [242, 316] as was stated by Dressick et al. [315] for (PAH

1306 + PSS)_n films, with the formation of bridges between amino groups of the PAH chains limiting
1307 the chains packing. This results in the formation of highly porous supramolecular films.

1308 4.7. pH

1309 The modification of the ionic equilibrium, and consequently of the effective charge of the
1310 building blocks by changing the pH presents a big importance on the assembly of polyelectrolyte
1311 multilayers, and in particular, when the assembly of weak polyelectrolytes, i.e. polyelectrolytes
1312 which a charge density tunable for the pH of the solutions, is concerned. The pH affects the
1313 degree of ionization of the polyelectrolyte chains, with the decrease of the latter driving a
1314 reduction of the polyelectrolyte solubility and their depletion from the solution. This is expected
1315 to enhance the deposition and increase the fuzziness of the obtained layers [51]. The
1316 understanding of the ionic equilibrium in the assembly of charged blocks is essential for using
1317 the pH as parameter for controlling the multilayer building. A simplified description of this ionic
1318 equilibrium is

1320 with *m* and *aq* being referred to the multilayer and aqueous phases, respectively, and *M* and *A*
1321 indicating the counterions of each polyelectrolyte and *Pol* with the positive and negative
1322 superindexes being the polycation and polyanion, respectively.

1323 It is worth mentioning that the bases underlying the effect of the pH changes on the assembly of
1324 multilayer involving weak polyelectrolytes can be understood in a similar way to that discussed
1325 for the effect of the ionic strength [51, 119]. The effect of the pH can be considered very
1326 important in multilayers involving PAH, PAA or different biopolymers. Guzman et al. [51]
1327 evidenced the strong effect of the pH on the ionization and solubility of PAA and CHI chains,
1328 which affect to the thickness of (PAA - CHI)_n multilayers. Furthermore, the modification of the
1329 pH can be used to induce a transition between different growth mechanisms as shown Bieker
1330 and Schönhoff [119] in (PAH + PAA)_n multilayers. Gong [317] showed that the surface
1331 morphology of multilayers of PDADMAC and poly(4-styrenesulfonic acid-*co*-maleic acid) can
1332 be modified by the assembly pH, with the roughness of the layers of PDADMAC (strong
1333 polyelectrolyte, non-pH sensitive) remaining unchanged with pH, whereas that of the polyanion
1334 layers, having a 50% of pH sensitive monomers (maleic acid monomers), increases with the pH
1335 as result of the worsening of the solubility of the copolymer which leads to a fuzzier structure of
1336 the copolymer-capped multilayers.

1337 **4.8. Temperature**

1338 The importance of the temperature on the assembly of polyelectrolyte multilayers has received
1339 less attention than other parameters. However, its impact on the control of the solubility of the
1340 polyelectrolyte can be even stronger than that reported for the pH or the ionic strength [120].
1341 This is clearly analyzing the particular case of (PAH - PSS)_n multilayers where the temperature
1342 is the most effective way to induce their non-linear growth. The transition between linear and
1343 non-linear growth mechanism can be also induced on (PDADMAC - PSS)_n multilayers by
1344 temperature changes [31, 185, 189], with the rate of exponential build up following a temperature
1345 dependant law $h(N+1)=h(N)e^{\beta N}$, where h indicates the thickness and N the number of deposited
1346 bilayers. β is the growth exponent which follows an Arrhenius-like dependence on $1/T$. This
1347 gives an indication of the enhanced ability of the polymer for overcoming activation barrier with
1348 the increase of T [120]. Thus, the increase of the temperature weaken the ionic pairing in the
1349 multilayers, making easier the mobility of the chains within the multilayer [219, 318].

1350

1351 **5. Physico-chemical properties of LbL multilayers**

1352 The discussion of the previous section has been devoted on the main physico-chemical aspects
1353 associated with the assembly of LbL multilayer. However, the understanding of the behavior of
1354 LbL materials is a challenge for both fundamental and applied science. Furthermore, the
1355 potential use of polyelectrolyte multilayers for a specific application requires a careful
1356 examination of their physico-chemical properties, and the procedures allowing one to tune such
1357 properties at will for obtaining materials with tailored properties. This section includes a brief
1358 discussion of some of the most important properties for the technological application of LbL
1359 films.

1360 **5.1. Water content: hydration and swelling**

1361 The water included within the multilayers is essential in the dynamic behavior of the films and
1362 their structure [49-51, 89, 107, 108, 311, 319-326]. This is the result of the impact of the water
1363 on the local molecular interactions, especially those related to the complexation between the
1364 polyelectrolytes during the assembly process [321, 325, 326]. It is worth mentioning that the
1365 water trapped in LbL materials affects to two different aspects of the multilayers: (i) hydration
1366 and (ii) swelling [320, 325, 326]. The dependence with the number of deposited layer of these
1367 two types of water was found to be the opposite [325, 326].

1368 Lösche et al. [106] using neutron reflectometry quantified a water content in (PAH-PSS)_n
1369 multilayers close to 40% of the total weight of the multilayer which corresponds to 8 water
1370 molecules per polyanion-polycation pair. For the case of (PDADMAC-PSS)_n multilayers, the
1371 number of water molecules per PDADMAC-PSS pair was found to be slightly lower (about 6),
1372 which is ascribed to the higher hydrophobicity of PDADMAC than PSS [110]. Most of
1373 polyelectrolyte multilayers present a relatively high water content, commonly between the 20
1374 and 80 % of the total weight of the films [49, 51, 107, 325, 326]. This is tunable by changing the
1375 conditions used during the assembly, mainly the charge density of the assembled blocks [321].
1376 The high weight fraction (X_w) of water on polyelectrolyte multilayers is essential for the
1377 properties of these systems, impacting decisively on aspects such as the encapsulation and
1378 release of active compounds from the assembled LbL materials. The water content of the films
1379 is strongly dependent on the multilayer thickness, and decreases as the thickness or the number
1380 of deposited layers increase as result of the material densification (see Figure 16) [107, 327]. It
1381 is worth mentioning that hydration water is asymmetrically distributed within the multilayer,
1382 with an even-odd dependence of the average water content of the multilayer on the nature of the
1383 outermost layer [312, 328]. This asymmetrical distribution of the hydration water and the key
1384 role of the last deposited layer in the hydration properties were confirmed by Ghostine et al.
1385 [236] and Lehaf et al. [235]. They show that the amount of water in (PDADMAC - PSS)_n
1386 multilayers is higher for PDADMAC-capped films than for those terminated in PSS. This is
1387 explained considering the different ability of the polyelectrolytes to associate water which agrees
1388 with the oscillation in the water mobility within the multilayer obtained by Schwarz and
1389 Schönhoff [322] using Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR).

1390 The high water content trapped within the multilayer during the process of assembly makes that
1391 this films can be considered as an example of gel-like materials, i.e. hydrated polyelectrolyte
1392 multilayers are plasticized materials [51]. This may be of interest for different applications in
1393 which the diffusion of small molecules along the film is required, e.g. drug delivery systems
1394 [113, 325, 326].

1395 The role of water in multilayers is not only the hydration and plastification of the films, playing
1396 an essential role in the degree of swelling of the materials [51, 107, 329]. This is strongly affected
1397 for the environmental conditions (e.g. relative humidity) and ionic strength of the solutions [330].
1398 This is again a result of the effect on the ionic strength on the ionic pairing between adjacent
1399 layers, and as matter of fact on the ionic cross-linking along the multilayer, which is expected to
1400 be critical on the control of the mechanical properties of the LbL materials [50, 51]. It is worth

1401 mentioning that the swelling of the multilayers is strongly affected for the interactions involved
1402 within the films, thus the nature of the building blocks will affect to the swelling degree of the
1403 multilayers [51, 240, 331].

1404
1405 Figure 16. Water content dependence on the number of bilayers for (PDADMAC - PSS)_n
1406 multilayers deposited from solutions with different ionic strength. Lines are guides for the eyes.
1407 Adapted from Ref. [107], Copyright 2011, with permission from The Royal Society of
1408 Chemistry.

1409

1410 5.2. Mechanical properties

1411 The mechanical properties of the LbL films play a central role for designing functional materials
1412 due to their importance on the control of the stability and the response of the materials against
1413 external perturbations [332, 333]. The mechanical properties are linked to both the hydration
1414 degree of the multilayers, and the specific interactions occurring within the multilayers. It was
1415 stated above that the high water content of the multilayers leads to their softening, and the
1416 mechanical response of the LbL films appears to be reminiscent to that found for gel-like or
1417 rubber-like materials, with viscoelastic modulus in the MPa range [51, 107]. However, the
1418 impact of the water content on the mechanical response of the multilayers makes possible to find
1419 dry films with a rigidity reminiscent of the behaviour of glass-like material [51, 107, 334, 335].
1420 Pavoov et al. [336] show for (PAH - PAA)_n multilayers that multilayers obtained under
1421 conditions ensuring a high charge density of the polyelectrolyte chains present a high ionic
1422 pairing, excluding water from the multilayers. This result in high values of the Young modulus

1423 obtained using quasi-static nano-indentation (up to 10 GPa for dry films, and two order of
 1424 magnitude lower for wet films). On the other side, the deposition of chains in a coiled
 1425 conformation results in a softening of the multilayers, and consequently in the decrease of the
 1426 Young modulus. This softening as result of the conformation of the deposited chains is illustrated
 1427 in the results of Figure 17 where the real, G' , and imaginary part, G'' , of the viscoelasticity shear
 1428 modulus obtained using a quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring for (CHI –
 1429 PAA)_n multilayers assembled under different pH conditions is displayed. The results show that
 1430 the deposition of layers with the chains in an extended conformation leads to $G' > G''$, with the
 1431 importance of G'' increasing as more coiled chains are deposited [51]. Similar results were
 1432 reported for the impact of the ionic strength on the mechanical properties of (PDADMAC-PSS)_n
 1433 multilayers [107].

1434
 1435 Figure 17. Mechanical properties of the PEI(CHI-PAA)_n multilayer fabricated under different
 1436 pH conditions as function of the thickness obtained using a dissipative quartz microbalance, h_{ac} .
 1437 (a) G' . (b) G'' . Adapted with permission from Ref. [51]. Copyright (2011) American Chemical
 1438 Society.

1439
 1440 It is worth mentioning that the type of substrates does not alter significantly the mechanical
 1441 response of polyelectrolyte multilayers [187], with this being generally only affected by the

1442 nature of the building blocks and the assembly conditions. This is clear analysing the impact of
1443 the increase of the ionic strength used for the assembly of (PDADMAC-PSS)_n multilayers on the
1444 mechanical properties of the films. The increase of the ionic strength drives a transition between
1445 a purely elastic materials to a fluid-like systems, which is explained in term of the weakening of
1446 the ionic pairing as results of a counterion-driven plasticizing. This agrees with the increase of
1447 the average water content of the multilayers. Therefore, the modification of any parameter that
1448 helps to the increase of the ionic pairing between the layers enhances the rigidity of the materials,
1449 whereas any plasticizer effects lead to worsening of this rigidity [51, 107, 187, 337]. This
1450 responsiveness can be used for the application of LbL materials in the biomedical field e.g. LbL
1451 materials for enhanced cells adhesion [330, 338].

1452 The role of the specific characteristic of the building blocks has been also reported as an aspect
1453 allowing the modification of the mechanical properties of the multilayers. Amorim et al. [339]
1454 have reported a decrease of the Young's modulus of (PLL-HA)_n multilayers with the increase of
1455 molecular weight of the HA used in agreement with the decrease of the hydration of the films.
1456 Another possibility for the modification of the mechanical properties of LbL films is the
1457 chemical cross-linking of the outermost layers. This enhances the rigidity of the multilayer, and
1458 limits the mobility of small molecules through it [104].

1459 **5.3. Porosity and permeability**

1460 Polyelectrolyte multilayers are soft materials, containing a high amount of water. Thus, it seems
1461 to be reasonable to analyse two aspects related to the density of the materials: porosity and and
1462 permeability. These characteristics play a key role for controlling the exchange of material
1463 between the inner region of the films or capsule and the surrounding environment, which present
1464 interest in encapsulation process but also for controlling the assembly process and interdiffusion
1465 of the polymer chains within the multilayers. It should be expected that rigid multilayers,
1466 presenting a high density and as matter of fact a low amount of retained water, results in the
1467 formations of non-porous films with a low permeability to molecules along the multi-layered
1468 shell.

1469 Several studies have shown that the porosity of LbL films can be tailored at will by controlling
1470 carefully the interactions and the choice of the building blocks [121, 332, 335]. This is clear from
1471 the different ability of filtration appearing in intrinsically- and extrinsically-compensated films,
1472 whereas in the former there is a strong influence on the permeation properties of the capping-
1473 layer, the permeability of the latter is governed by the bulk region of the multilayer [340].

1474 Furthermore, the porosity of the obtained materials can be reversibly tuned by changing the ionic
1475 strength, pH, temperature, light, ultrasound, magnetic field or mechanical deformation [121].
1476 Antipov et al. [332] showed that the porosity of polyelectrolyte multilayers may be reversibly
1477 triggered by changing the pH of the surrounding environment due to the modification of the ionic
1478 equilibrium within the multilayer. The selective and tunable permeability of polyelectrolyte
1479 multilayers has been recently probed for films of fucoidan and CHI [341]. The chemical nature
1480 of the last layer was found to be essential in the control of the swelling degree of the multilayer.
1481 Furthermore, the obtained multilayers present size exclusion ability for the penetration of
1482 proteins. Thus, whereas lysozyme can permeate and diffuse through the multilayers, bovine
1483 serum albumin cannot penetrate into the multilayer. This is indication that specific multilayers
1484 may be used for the retention of small proteins and their release upon demand as response to
1485 different physico-chemical stimuli.

1486 It is worth mentioning that any factor enabling an enhancement of the film rigidity reduces the
1487 permeability of LbL films [121, 342]. This is clear from the studies by Yang et al. [342]. They
1488 found that the cross-linking of (PEI-PAA)_n multilayers with glutaraldehyde results in a decrease
1489 of the porosity of the films and as matter of fact of their permeability. This agree with the results
1490 by Leahaf et al. [331]. They analysed the dependence of the salt diffusion along the multilayer on
1491 the mechanical properties of the films and found that the increase of the rigidity was detrimental
1492 for ions permeability. Brinke et al. [343, 344] have took advantage of the above characteristic
1493 for the fabrication of asymmetric membranes (Chimera membranes), where the deposition of
1494 layers with a gradient permeability obtained as results of their assembly under different
1495 conditions or even by their different chemical nature, allows the fabrication of materials with
1496 enhanced separation properties.

1497 **5.4. Osmotic response**

1498 The discussion of the previous section showed that the modification of the ionic equilibrium
1499 during the assembly of polyelectrolyte multilayers impact decisively on the fabrication and
1500 properties of the films. This is because the degree of swelling-shrinking of the multilayers is
1501 associated with the ionic content of the inner region of the films which affects to the osmotic
1502 stress. Therefore, it should be expected that the osmotic response of a preformed LbL material
1503 may be associated with any stimuli changing the ionic equilibrium within the film (ionic strength,
1504 pH, etc.) [107, 185]. Different studies have pointed out that the modification of the ionic
1505 equilibrium in pre-formed multilayers leads to modifications on the films which present sign

1506 than that occurring in polyelectrolytes in solution or in polyelectrolyte adsorbing from a solution
1507 onto a surface (anti-polyelectrolyte behaviour) [107, 185].

1508 The exposure of (PDADMAC - PSS)_n or (PAH + PSS)_n multilayers to water results in a swelling
1509 of the film due to the counterions release which is required to ensure an equality on the chemical
1510 potential of the ions inside the multilayer and in the aqueous environment. The opposite
1511 phenomena was found when the water is replaced by solution containing salt. This results in the
1512 up-taking of counterions for the multilayers which leads to the collapse of the multilayers. It is
1513 worth mentioning that this osmotic response, trying to equilibrate the ionic equilibrium, is
1514 strongly dependent on the ionic pairing existing within the multilayer and the magnitude of the
1515 induced perturbation, presenting in most the cases an almost completely reversibility [107, 185].
1516 Figure 18 shows the dependence of the osmotic response for (PDADMAC-PSS)_n multilayers,
1517 obtained as the change on the thickness of the films, after their exposure first to water, and then
1518 to a salt solution with the same ionic strength used on the multilayer fabrication. The results
1519 evidence that the osmotic shocks is smaller when the modification of the ionic strength is smaller.

1520
1521 Figure 18. Changes on the thickness measured by ellipsometry as result of a osmotic stresses for
1522 (PDADMAC - PSS)_n multilayers built using two different ionic strength. For films built using
1523 [NaCl] = 100 mM ■ and ● represent the changes in the thickness when the salt solution is
1524 replaced for pure water and the inverse process, respectively and for films built using [NaCl] =
1525 300 mM ▽ and ◇ represent the changes when the salt solution is replaced for pure water and the
1526 inverse process, respectively. Adapted from Ref. [107], Copyright (2009), with permission from
1527 The Royal Society of Chemistry.

1528

1529 There are some cases in which the introduction of an osmotic stress may result on partial
1530 dissolution of the multilayer as was shown by Mjahed et al. [335] for (PLL-HA)_n multilayers.
1531 The exposure of such multilayers to ionic strengths above a critical value of 0.3 M results in the
1532 formation of holes within the multilayer. The ionic pairing has been stated above as a critical
1533 parameter for tuning the swelling degree of polyelectrolytes multilayers, thus it is expected that
1534 the swelling can be reduced by a chemical cross-linking between adjacent layers [345]. It is
1535 worth noting that the above discussed modifications on the swelling of the multilayers can be a
1536 very useful alternative for controlling the release profiles of encapsulated compounds within the
1537 multilayer because it affects to the permeability and porosity of the films.

1538

1539 **6. Applications**

1540 The fabrication of both passive and active (“smart materials”) nanomaterials by the LbL method
1541 and their applications in different areas of the nanotechnology have undergone a spectacular in
1542 recent years [30, 31]. The design of such materials take advantage of the possibility to control
1543 the film composition along the thickness of the designed supramolecular material, and
1544 consequently their properties. Furthermore, the LbL is a simple, fast and cheap approach for the
1545 assembly of materials which has fostered the research on its technological applications.
1546 However, even though the LbL design of functional materials has been developed as a key
1547 enabling technology, the next goal for the LbL technology remains the design and fabrication of
1548 3D ordered nanostructures with real-life applications, which makes it necessary to ensure the
1549 scalability of the LbL approach to the industrial level [346]. This is important because the LbL
1550 approach provides the bases for controlling the physico-chemical properties of multifunctional
1551 materials in such a way which is impossible to attain using other methods such as solution
1552 casting, vacuum-assisted filtration or chemical vapor deposition [72]. This section presents a
1553 short revision of some of the most promising applications of electrostatically assembled LbL
1554 materials. It is true that the applications of LbL multilayers based only in polyelectrolytes is
1555 rather limited. Therefore, some examples of applications in which at least one of the
1556 polyelectrolyte is replaced by other type of building blocks will be discussed.

1557 **6.1. Layer-by-Layer materials for encapsulation**

1558 The fabrication of LbL materials as encapsulation platforms (cargo systems) needs a carefully
1559 examination of the specific field of application of the prepared system [41]. The use of the

1560 multilayers of LbL deposited onto macroscopic flat templates as cargo systems requires the
1561 inclusion of the molecules to be encapsulated either as an independent layer included within the
1562 layer stacking or blended with one of the building blocks of the multilayer [50, 51]. This types
1563 of material are able to release the encapsulated compound as result of a partial destruction of
1564 their structure by a specific external stimuli, e.g. changes in pH, ionic strength, or temperature,
1565 photo-dissociation, biodegradation of the material, etc. [347, 348]. Sun et al. [349]used the above
1566 discussed approach for the encapsulation and release of different doxorubicin hydrochloride
1567 from multilayers of CHI and different polyanions (HA, AG and tannic acid). The degradation of
1568 the above multilayers upon their exposure to saline solutions of high pH results in the fast
1569 degradation of the multilayers which results in the release of the encapsulated. This can be
1570 modify changing the ionic density, molecular structure and functional groups of the
1571 polyelectrolytes, with these aspects affecting the morphology, porosity, thickness and physico-
1572 chemical properties of the multilayers.

1573 The fabrication of micro- and nano-capsules using the LbL method is a more promising
1574 alternative for many technological fields, and in particular for biomedical applications [41, 347].
1575 The research on the applicability of LbL capsules in practical medical situations has received a
1576 great interest in recent years [4, 350]. One of the first approaches for the fabrication of capsules
1577 by the LbL approach was focused in the assembly of LbL shells onto small drug particles (micro-
1578 or nano-meter size drug particles with poor solubility in water). This methodology has been
1579 applied for the encapsulation of a broad range materials (anticancer drugs, anticorrosion agents,
1580 insoluble dyes, and inorganic salts), enabling a significant enhancement of the dispersion ability
1581 of the drug in aqueous medium, e.g. the stability of silver nanoparticles in saline medium was
1582 found to be significantly enhanced by the deposition of a LbL shell of CHI and dextran [351].
1583 Furthermore, this type of encapsulation approach ensures a high loading rate of the drugs (70 –
1584 80 wt %). An alternative approach to the above described involves the deposition of multilayers
1585 onto sacrificial cores (polymer or ceramic particles) in which the drug may be incorporated [87,
1586 352]. This requires to remove the template once the polyelectrolyte shell is built and before the
1587 encapsulation of the molecule. The encapsulation and release of the molecules is attained by
1588 controlling the thickness of the multilayer shell and its chemical composition, which can affect
1589 to the distribution profile of the encapsulated within the film [353]. This latter approach results
1590 in a poorer encapsulation efficiency than the previous one (about 5 – 10 wt %), even though the
1591 encapsulation of many chemical using this approach has been possible: ibuprofen, furosemide,
1592 nifedipine, naproxen, biotin, vitamin K3, insulin, demathasone, tamoxifen, paclitaxel, and

1593 curcumin, DNA fragments, peptides and other therapeutic agents [354, 355]. Selina et al. [356]
1594 extended the use of LbL materials on the encapsulation of vaccines with promising results in
1595 their preliminary *in vivo* tests using LbL capsules loaded with a plasmid DNA against swine
1596 fever. However, the effectiveness of the application of LbL materials as encapsulation platforms,
1597 especially for drugs, has associated an additional challenge: the incorporation of specific
1598 functionalities favoring molecular recognition processes between the cargo systems and the cells
1599 or tissues.

1600 It is worth mentioning that the above discussed methodology for the fabrication of capsules is
1601 not limited to the use spherical colloidal particles as templates. Ai et al. [357] fabricated multi-
1602 layered polyelectrolyte nanotubes by replication on the inner walls of the pores of alumina
1603 templates by alternate deposition of PAH and PSS, followed by the template removal. The
1604 obtained nanotubes were found to present a rather thick walls, a high mechanical stability and
1605 flexibility. More interesting from the biomedical point of view are the nanotubes of poly(L-
1606 arginine) and human serum albumin obtained by Komatsu et al. [358] using nanoporous
1607 polycarbonate membranes a template. This type of nanotubes evidenced a high effectiveness in
1608 the removal of viral genome from solutions of Hepatitis B virus.

1609 The preparation of LbL capsules requires to consider the role of the interaction between the
1610 different templates units in addition to those interactions commonly appearing during the
1611 fabrication of LbL materials (assembled block – assembled block, assembled block – solvent
1612 and assembled block – template interactions). These template-template interactions may drive
1613 the formation of aggregates where the association between the different units can occur through
1614 interactions with different strengths, which may induce the fusion or coalescence of soft
1615 templates (vesicles/liposomes or emulsion droplets). This may interfere with the assembly
1616 process, and reduces the concentration of capsules [42].

1617 The correct protection of the encapsulated compounds requires the deposition of a minimal
1618 number layers (commonly around 15 layers) [359]. Additional parameters to consider on the use
1619 of LbL materials for encapsulation purpose are the surface charge of the outermost layer, and the
1620 degree of swelling and cross-linking of the films, with the latter being correlated to the
1621 mechanical properties of the cargo systems. This may modify the release profiles of the
1622 encapsulated materials [360]. The control of the above parameters can be performed either
1623 during the assembly process or after the multilayer fabrication (post-treatment) by the changing
1624 environmental parameters (ionic strength, temperature, pH, solvent quality, etc). This induces a

1625 reversible modification on the swelling degree of the capsule which may contribute to the control
1626 of the release processes [361]. Antipov et al. [332] showed that the release of encapsulated
1627 fluorescein from (PAH - PSS)_n capsules was reduced as the thickness of the multilayer shell
1628 increase. This may be rationalized considering the increase of the cross-linking between the
1629 layers which leads to a reduction of the permeability of the films. Similar effects were found in
1630 relation to the dissolution of calcium oxalate crystals, and the subsequent release of the small
1631 inorganic cations formed as result of the decomposition process [362].

1632 The use of LbL materials has solved, at least partially, the difficulties of the control of the release
1633 mechanism appearing in most of the traditional systems used for encapsulation. These latter
1634 present release profiles mediated by the erosion of the capsule or the free diffusion of the
1635 molecules through the shells, which results in most of the case to burst release and poor efficient
1636 of the formulations. However, the stimuli responsiveness of LbL materials allow, in many cases,
1637 triggering the release using different physical (temperature, light, ultrasounds, magnetic fields,
1638 mechanical deformation) or chemical (ionic solvent, pH, solvent quality, electrochemistry)
1639 stimuli or even by the living tissues itself, which can be used either for the encapsulation or the
1640 controlled release and specific targeting [359, 363, 364]. The type of stimuli used is generally
1641 related to the specific nature of the materials, both encapsulated one and those forming the
1642 capsule, with the release of the compound being expanded in time-scales in the 1 – 100 hours
1643 range. Furthermore, an important advantage of the responsiveness of LbL materials for
1644 encapsulation is the possibility to switch on and off the release upon demand [32, 365]. Shen et
1645 al. produced (PAH-PSS)_n capsules loaded bovine serum albumin which can be used for loading
1646 doxorubicin by the increase of pH of the medium. The release of the drug can be also controlled
1647 by the change of the pH due to the modification of the electrostatic interaction between the drug
1648 and the capsule [366]. The change of pH was also chosen by De Geest et al. [367] for triggering
1649 the release of encapsulated compounds from LbL shells formed by poly(L-arginine) and dextran.
1650 They optimize their fabrication process to ensure a release induced by the local pH of the target
1651 tissues or cells.

1652 The stimuli responsiveness of LbL multilayers can also be an advantage to facilitate the
1653 distribution of the encapsulated compounds towards specific targets. This was used by Podgórna
1654 and Szczepanowicz [368] including Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles into (PLL-PGA)_n LbL capsules to
1655 transport the capsules to an specific target taking advantage of the responsiveness of the particles
1656 to magnetic fields. The use of light sensitive materials (mainly to low intensity UV radiation or
1657 near infrared radiation) on the fabrication of LbL capsules have also allowed the transport of the

1658 nanocapsules to a specific target, which open important possibilities for designing materials with
1659 specific targeting abilities [369]. Cheng et al. [370] demonstrated that the application of an
1660 electrical field allows triggering the release of gene material (DNA) from its electrostatically
1661 assembled multilayers with PEI. The next step for the application of LbL capsules is the
1662 fabrication of smart systems enabling the triggering of the release as result of their expose to
1663 several stimuli, which provides the bases for an appropriate mimicking of the natural systems
1664 [361, 364].

1665 There is a growing interest for the encapsulation of poorly soluble compounds using the liquid
1666 environment of oil in water emulsions, where the multi-layered shell provides the protection of
1667 the encapsulated compounds, stabilizing the emulsions [359, 371]. This type of encapsulation
1668 systems open new perspective for manufacturing nano-containers which can retain the
1669 encapsulated compounds during long times, presenting a fast release upon demand [163].

1670 The fabrication of multicapsules or multicompartmental cargo systems (capsosomes) based in
1671 the assembly of LbL materials combining multiple subunits such as polyelectrolyte layers,
1672 liposomes, and nanoparticles presents also a big interest. The most general approach for
1673 preparing this type of multicompartmental systems involves the coating of a colloidal template
1674 combining multiple layers of polymers and intact vesicles, which provides the bases for
1675 overcoming some of the limitation associated with the application of the individual materials,
1676 e.g. the poor mechanical stability of the liposomes. Once the multi-layered structure is formed,
1677 the template is removed using the appropriate procedures [98, 99, 101].

1678 **6.2. Layer by Layer on the fabrication of biocompatible and anti-fouling materials**

1679 The versatility of the LbL approach for fabricating materials combining building blocks
1680 presenting different physico-chemical properties allows manufacturing materials where the
1681 interaction of the materials with cells and tissues is required, including coatings for bone
1682 repairing, vascular engineering, tracheal prostheses or dental applications [346, 372-375]. The
1683 adhesion, proliferation and differentiation of cells onto polyelectrolyte multilayers is strongly
1684 dependent on the film nature, with the multilayer stiffness being critical for their application as
1685 substrate for cell culture [376-378]. Furthermore, the use of LbL materials enables the
1686 introduction of nutrients, genetic materials or different ligands within the cell culture
1687 environment. The use of LbL coatings formed by chitosan and an elastin-like biopolymer onto
1688 titanium dental implants was found to be a good alternative for the improvement of the
1689 biomineralization and differentiation of osteoblast [379]. LbL coatings formed by 10 bilayers of

1690 the PSS-PAH pair onto a polyetheretherketone implant was found to improve the cell adhesion
1691 and osseointegration [380]. LbL multilayers can be also useful for improving the cellular
1692 proliferation onto cardiovascular implants as was evidenced by Meng et al [381]. They used
1693 (CHI – HEP)_n multilayers to coat stainless steel stents, with such coated stent presenting an
1694 enhanced affinity for endothelial affinity and thrombus resistance. This facilitates its adhesion
1695 to porcine iliac artery endothelial cells and their proliferation onto the coated stent surface (from
1696 20% for the bare metal stent to 60-70% for the coated one).

1697 The antimicrobial properties of implants can be also improved by the use of LbL coatings. The
1698 LbL films can face these issue, minimizing the adhesion of the microorganism and killing them
1699 by contact or by the release of active compounds close to the implant [382]. Shi et al. [383]
1700 showed that the fabrication coatings formed by LbL multi-layered structures of collagen and a
1701 cationic antimicrobial peptide on titanium dental implants using allows the reduction of the
1702 proliferation of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Porphyromonas gingivalis*. The deposition of
1703 multilayers of lysozyme and collagen onto composite fibers of silk fibroin and nylon 6 was a
1704 good alternative to improve the biocompatibility (a significant enhance of the fibroblast
1705 proliferation was found in relation to the bare fibers) and mechanical properties of the fiber,
1706 reducing the proliferation of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* by a 70 and 10%,
1707 respectively, in relation to the uncoated fibers [384]. Martins et al. [385] show that multilayers
1708 of carrageenan and CHI can be used as scaffolds for tissue engineering, inhibiting the attachment
1709 and growth of different bacteria.

1710 The fabrication of antifouling surfaces aimed to the minimization of the adhesion of organic
1711 materials is another active field of application of LbL films. It was shown that (PAH - PSS)_n
1712 multilayers capped by phosphorylcholine and poly(ethylenoxide) can be used for mimicking the
1713 antifouling components of the erythrocyte membranes and limit protein adhesion [386].
1714 Similarly, the combination of LbL polyelectrolyte layers of with a final poly(ethylene-glycol)
1715 capping layers was demonstrated to be a good choice for protecting nanolipid carriers loaded
1716 with doxorubicin, ensuring their stabilization in the blood stream for long periods of time [387].
1717 Multilayers combining polysaccharides present good properties against the adhesion of serum
1718 proteins, and their application onto prosthesis surfaces enhances their thrombi-resistance [374,
1719 388]. This is the result of the high hydration of polysaccharide multilayers. It is worth mentioning
1720 that the antifouling properties of LbL materials may be improved by the increase of the density
1721 of the films [389].

1722 Etienne et al. [390, 391] show that the growth and proliferation of bacteria onto surface may be
1723 prevented using LbL films decorated with defensin and chromofungin. Similarly, Kim et al.
1724 [373] pointed out that the proliferation of smooth muscle cell onto stent surfaces may be hindered
1725 using multilayers formed by polylysine and hyaluronic acid-grafted-poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid)
1726 and loaded with heparin and paclitaxel. The use of multilayers formed by HEP and collagen onto
1727 titanium cardiovascular implants was found to inhibit the adhesion and proliferation of platelets,
1728 improving the blood compatibility of the metal [392].

1729 **6.3. Layer-by-Layer materials on the fabrication of membranes**

1730 The use of polyelectrolyte multilayers have been frequently for manufacturing membranes for
1731 different purposes [31]. LbL films have evidenced a good performance on the selective
1732 separation of different pollutant species, e.g. pollutants from water [32, 393-395] or as
1733 membranes for pervaporation or ultrafiltration purposes [32, 365]. Furthermore, the good
1734 performance of (PAH-PSS)_n multilayers in electroosmotic was evidenced by Qi et al. [396].
1735 They showed that the performance of the membranes depends on both the number of deposited
1736 layers and the nature of the outermost layer. Shi et al. [397] showed that polyelectrolyte
1737 multilayers of a sulfonated pentablock copolymer and PEI on hydrolyzed polyacrylonitrile fibers
1738 may be an very useful tool for dehydrating fuel via pervaporation,

1739 LbL films are a promising tool for the fabrication of membraned for pressure-driven desalination,
1740 mainly membranes for reverse and forward osmosis [398]. Zhang et al. [399] showed that porous
1741 membranes coated by a multilayer of polyvinylamine and polyvinylsulfate presented a good
1742 performance in both reverse and forward osmosis, with its rejection of MgCl₂ and MgSO₄ being
1743 almost independent of concentration of the feed solution or the operating pressure. However, the
1744 permeation of other salts, such as NaCl and Na₂SO₄, was found to be strongly dependent on the
1745 operational parameters. However, even though the above membranes present under specific
1746 conditions good salt rejection, the water flux is low. An important drawback to the use of LbL
1747 films in desalination process is that they are easily destroyed under severe conditions, including
1748 high ionic strengths or chlorine treatments. This makes it necessary to improve their stability by
1749 cross-linking processes [400, 401]. Qiu et al. [400] showed that the use of membranes formed
1750 by PAH and PSS cross-linked with glutaraldehyde leads to a significant enhancement of the
1751 MgCl₂ in relation to their non-cross-linked counterpart. However, the water permeability of the
1752 rejection layers was significantly reduced.

1753 Qi et al. [396] showed that the dependence of the properties of the capping layer can influence
1754 decisively on the application of (PAH-PSS)_n in the fabrication of forward osmosis membranes,
1755 allowing a controlled modification of the hydraulic permeability and the solute permeability.
1756 This was explained in terms of a complex interplay of interactions between the electrolytic
1757 solutions and multilayer. Furthermore, the efficiency of the membrane was found to be easily
1758 controllable by tuning the number of deposited layers or the chemical nature of the capping layer.

1759 Lee et al. [402] took advantage on the LbL approach for fabricating (PAH-PAA)_n multilayers
1760 loaded with methylene blue and heparin onto electrospun polyacrylonitrile fibers. The obtained
1761 membranes showed good antifouling and anticoagulation properties, i.e. good blood
1762 compatibility. This makes them a good alternative for their use as biomedical membranes for
1763 hemodialysis.

1764 Additional applications of the membranes obtained using the LbL method are the fabrication of
1765 chiral membranes for separation of optical active compounds [372], membranes for selective ion
1766 separation [376] or membranes for the optimization of the proton transport in fuel cells [377].

1767 **6.4. Layer-by-Layer materials for the fabrication of self-healing and anti-corrosion** 1768 **coatings**

1769 The LbL method has been developed as a powerful tool on the fabrication of self-healing
1770 materials because it allows the introduction of nano-reservoirs or nano-reactors within the
1771 multilayer structure which may provide a self-healing character to the manufactured materials
1772 [403-405]. The activation of the healing characteristics of nano-reservoirs is generally triggered
1773 by external stimuli with physical, chemical or mechanical origin. Shchukin et al. [406] showed
1774 that polyelectrolyte multilayers with self-healing properties may protect to aluminium surfaces
1775 against corrosion.

1776 Moreover, polyelectrolyte multilayers can present intrinsic self-healing properties, which may
1777 be related to the dynamics of the polyelectrolytes chains within the multilayer, i.e. the mobility
1778 of the chains in the hydrated environment of the multilayer can help on the healing of the films
1779 after a surface damage [404]. The self-healing character of (PEI-PAA)_n multilayers triggered by
1780 the water penetration in the internal regions of the films was observed by Wang et al. [407], with
1781 the water penetration favoring the interdiffusion of the polyelectrolytes from the internal layers
1782 to the outermost region of the multilayers. However, the self-healing of polyelectrolyte
1783 multilayers depend on their structure and thickness, with the existence a strong cross-linking in

1784 the structure reducing the self-healing properties of the films as result of a hindered interdiffusion
1785 of the chains. This allows rationalizing the limited self-healing properties of (PDADMAC -
1786 PSS)_n multilayers in term of the strong interactions between the polyelectrolyte chains once the
1787 multilayers is formed [408], which limits the self-healing on polyelectrolyte multilayers to those
1788 involving weak polyelectrolytes [404]. Recently, Yuan et al. [409] prepared LbL multilayers
1789 using a peptide modified carboxymethyl chitosan and dopamine modified oxidized alginate
1790 (OALG-D). These multilayers evidenced a significant cell adhesion for human dermal fibroblast,
1791 holding high self-healing and radical scavenging abilities. These characteristics make the
1792 multilayers a promising alternative for regenerative medicine applications.

1793 The LbL multilayers have been also applied on the fabrication of anticorrosion protective
1794 coatings. Farhat and Schlenoff [410] showed that the fabrication of a (PDADMAC-PSS)_n
1795 multilayer with ten bilayers onto stainless steel surfaces allows a significant reduction of the
1796 metal corrosion, with the anticorrosion properties being improved for intrinsically compensated
1797 multilayers where the permeability is significantly reduced due to the strong ionic pairing
1798 between polyelectrolytes in adjacent layers. The fabrication of multilayers containing
1799 hydrophobic polyelectrolytes - (poly(N-octadecyl-2-ethynyl-pyridinium bromide)-poly(ether-
1800 ether-ketone sulfonate))_n or (poly(vinyl-pyridine)-PSS)_n- are a good alternative for anticorrosion
1801 protection [410].

1802 Udoh et al. [411] tested, very recently, the ability of multilayers formed by different
1803 combinations of polyelectrolytes loaded with mesoporous silica particles containing
1804 benzotriazole as self-healing protective anticorrosion coatings for aluminum alloys, and found
1805 that multilayers formed by two weak polyelectrolytes release the healing compounds faster than
1806 multilayers combining weak and strong polyelectrolytes, with the later allowing for a more
1807 controlled and prolonged release. Furthermore, it was found that the anticorrosion properties was
1808 strongly dependent on the nature of the multilayer and the number of polyelectrolyte layers.

1809 **6.5. Layer-by-Layer materials in the fabrication of superhydrophobic/superhydrophilic** 1810 **coating**

1811 The fabrication of superhydrophobic and superhydrophilic surfaces by the LbL approach
1812 requires the combination of polyelectrolytes and nanoparticles to control the roughness of the
1813 films, and minimize the contact angle hysteresis [236, 412]. (PAH-PAA)_n multilayers with
1814 embedded silica nanoparticles and capped with a fluorinated copolymer allow fabricating
1815 superhydrophobic coatings with a contact angle around of 175° [413]. The inclusion of ZrO₂

1816 particles on (PAH-PAA)_n multilayers allows fabricating surfaces with a good water repellency.
1817 This is strongly correlated to the number of deposited (at least 20 bilayers are needed for an
1818 optimal repellency) and the nature of the last layer (PAH-capped multilayers evidenced better
1819 repellency) [414]. Han et al. [415] showed that multilayers the wettability properties of the
1820 multilayers combining PAH and silica nanoparticles can be reversibly modified from
1821 superhydrophobic (contact angle > 165°) to superhydrophilic (contact angle < 10°) by exposure to
1822 UV-ozone plasma.

1823 Huang et al. [416] shows that textured (PAH-PAA)_n multilayers allows the manufacturing of
1824 omniphobic and slippery (slip angle for water and oils around 3), with the type of texture being tuned
1825 by change of pH. (PAH-PAA)_n multilayers were also used by Guo et al. [417] to create self-
1826 cleaning surfaced as were shown by. They coated electrospun polyacrylonitrile fibers with this
1827 type of multilayers, and found that the coated fibers present a good ability to separate oil-water
1828 mixtures and emulsions with high flux and oil recovery efficiency under intermittent pressure.
1829 This is due to their superamphiphobic properties. Thus the obtained structures present both air
1830 superhydrophilicity and a complete oil repellency when they are wetted by water i.e. underwater
1831 superoleophobicity. Furthermore, the coated fibers have excellent self-cleaning properties.

1832 It is worth mentioning that the above discussion on the possible applications of LbL materials in
1833 different technological fields is not intended to be exhaustive and only selected cases have been
1834 chosen. The list of possible applications of LbL materials also include energy storage devices,
1835 chemical and biological sensors or high-strength composite films, to cite some examples [4, 6,
1836 72, 418]. However, the detailed discussion of the multiple potential applications of LbL materials
1837 may result in several reviews, and remains far from the scope of this review.

1838

1839 **7. Concluding remarks**

1840 This review has examined some of the most fundamental bases of the Layer-by-Layer method
1841 for the fabrication of multi-layered systems, paying special attention to the analysis of the
1842 building process, properties and potential applications of systems involving polyelectrolytes, the
1843 so-called polyelectrolyte multilayer. This is a rapidly evolving field which difficulties the task
1844 of presenting a comprehensive description of these systems, hence this work tries to provide a
1845 general perspective of the current knowledge on this broad field.

1846 The simplicity, flexibility and versatility of the LbL method have resulted in a strong
1847 development, which leads to a continuous appearance of new concepts, procedures and
1848 applications enabling the fabrication of functional nanomaterials with a broad range of properties
1849 and structures. This has required a careful examination of the complex physico-chemical bases
1850 underlying the assembly process. The formation of polyelectrolyte multilayers is possible
1851 through a complex interplay of different contributions -electrostatic interactions (enthalpic
1852 contribution) vs. entropic contributions- that determines the ionic pairing, the growth and
1853 structure of the obtained multilayers, and their physico-chemical properties. It is clear that only
1854 from the understanding of the interactions involved in the assembly process is possible to
1855 understand the particular characteristics of this type of systems, which help on the control of the
1856 distribution of the polyelectrolyte during the fabrication of the multilayer and consequently of
1857 the multilayer structure (stratification of the layers). The control of such aspect opens many
1858 routes to the application of polyelectrolyte multilayers in different industrial and technological
1859 fields. It is true that the use of the LbL approach on the fabrication of functional materials may
1860 be a promising starting point for the nano-architectonics, i.e. the combination of the
1861 nanotechnological concepts with other scientific fields (organic chemistry, supramolecular
1862 chemistry, and biotechnology) for the fabrication of materials. However, the extensive research
1863 efforts made in the understanding of the physico-chemical bases of the building of
1864 polyelectrolyte multilayers cannot hide the lack of knowledge remaining in some particular
1865 aspects, especially related to the adsorption dynamics, which is an important drawback for the
1866 development of real applications of these systems.

1867

1868 **Acknowledgements**

1869 This work was funded by MINECO under grant CTQ2016-78895-R and by Banco Santander-
1870 Universidad Complutense grant PR87/19-22513. We are grateful to C.A.I. Espectroscopia from
1871 the UCM for the use of their facilities.

1872

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